

Generations and Gender Survey

Baseline Questionnaire

Version 3.1.1

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Citation

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Please note that this is the final version of the questionnaire. It incorporates a series of corrections as well as changes that were documented in version 3.0.7

This version also includes a small number of optional items marked in grey. These are items related to the Theory of Planned Behaviour for fertility. The items FER25, FER26, and FER27 can either be deleted entirely or shortened by deleting items FER25g and FER25h as well as FER26 (items c, d, g and i). Moreover, the item INC04 is also optional. It is a useful multi-item question to capture social exclusion. However, to shorten the questionnaire it can be omitted.

Items related to the SDG 5.6.1. are marked in blue. These are important but sensitive items. Countries might have to take extra measures in view of their sensitivity. Specifically, these are items FER28, FER29 and WEL02a.

Short history of the Baseline questionnaire

The new Baseline questionnaire builds on previous versions of the questionnaire and has involved various groups, developments and testing phases. This can be summarized in four main phases:

- **Phase I: Original questionnaire (GGS-I):**

The original questionnaire was developed based on the inputs of various people involved in the setting up of the GGP. The main background document was published in 2005. As compared to the previous Family and Fertility (Survey), a number of key innovations were introduced, including: the panel (prospective) dimension, the extension of the age group from 18 to 79 years old, a broader conceptualization of factors influencing fertility and family-related decisions (e.g. health and well-being), and the adoption of the Theory of Planned Behaviour to analyze demographic intentions and behaviour. In addition, the Contextual Database was developed as a key instrument to analyze micro-macro linkages. This original questionnaire was used through the Round 1 (GGS-I) in nearly 20 countries. An overview of the survey instrument and assessment of this first round of data collection can be found in the publications listed below.

- UNECE (2005). Generations and Gender Programme: Survey Instruments. Online: https://www.unece.org/pau/pub/ggp_survey_instruments.html
- Vergauwen, J., Wood, J., De Wachter, D., & Neels, K. (2015). Quality of demographic data in GGS Wave 1. *Demographic Research*, 32, 723-774. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26350130>
- Fokkema, T., Kveder, A., Hiekel, N., Emery, T., & Liefbroer, A. C. (2016). Generations and Gender Programme Wave 1 data collection: An overview and assessment of sampling and fieldwork methods, weighting procedures, and cross-sectional representativeness. *Demographic Research*, 34, 499-524. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26332044>

- **Phase II: Intermediate version 2.7:**

In 2009, the GGP was awarded a Design Study grant¹ to further develop the GGP as a research infrastructure. During this period, a questionnaire working group (2009-12) was formed to make small amendments to the questionnaire including some of the lessons learnt from the assessment of the Round 1. Some of the key changes introduced include a new social network module, measures of how societal constraints and social policies influence decisions on family formation and retirement and a personality module. An overview of the changes can be found in Caporali (2017). Importantly, this new version was tested online in a small pilot survey in Slovenia. A similar version was also used in **Belarus (2017), Latvia (pilot 2018), and Kazakhstan (2019)**.

- Caporali, A. (2017). Innovations introduced with the new Questionnaire. Online: <https://www.ggp-i.org/data/methodology/>

- **Phase III: Development and testing of the new Baseline:**

This phase extended from 2017 to 2020 and was partly financed by a grant from the European Commission². It included various steps.

- a. First, the intermediate version (above) was coded in Blaise and tested in **the Push-to-Web Three-country Pilot**. Results from this Pilot can be found [here](#). During this period, the questionnaire was slightly amended based on discussions with partners involved in the Pilot.
- b. A Questionnaire Task Force (Mills, Lugtig, Gauthier, Bujard) was appointed and met multiple times to reflect on the lessons learnt in the Pilot (including breakoffs, etc.), introduce amendments to the questionnaire to correct some errors, take into account feedback from Users, and introduce some elements of innovations. It also endorsed the idea of making it possible for national teams to include a few country-specific questions which could be added to the core questionnaire. The resulting core questionnaire (version 3.0) was then discussed and adopted by the GGP Consortium Board in December 2019.
- c. The adopted questionnaire then entered an extended **period of testing** including internal testing by the GGP central Hub team, testing by

¹ "Generations and Gender Programme: A European Research Infrastructure on the Causes and Consequences of Demographic Developments", FP7 grant no. 212749 (FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES - Specific Programme "Capacities": Research infrastructures).

² "Generations and Gender Programme: Evaluate, Plan, Initiate". Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, grant no. 739511 (INFRADEV-02-2016 – Preparatory Phase and support of ESFRI projects)

Partners, external testing by a survey agency, and consultation with Users. During each of these phases amendments were introduced including to the wording, coding, and filters. During this time, the questionnaire was used in Moldova (2020).

- d. **A second Questionnaire Task Force** was then appointed in 2019 (Lappegard, Lugtig, Luck, Makay, Gauthier) with a view towards approving the final amendments (step c). However during this time, the Task Force also decided to devote time to the **length of the questionnaire** especially in view of the fact that several countries were planning to carry the survey online. With a history of Face-to-Face mode of data collection, the average duration (around 52 minutes) had never been the focus of extensive discussion. This was also not the focus of the Push-to-Web Pilot (referred to above). The Task Force was unanimous in that the questionnaire was too long, especially for a web version. This sentiment was also echoed during the GGP Council of Partners meeting of June 2020. The Task Force met multiple times to tackle the issue. This was particularly difficult work in view of the history of the questionnaire (where all sections and subsections had a clear purpose). At the end, the Task Force agreed on a set of cuts which preserved the integrity of the version 3.0 questionnaire, but did introduce cuts in some of the long sections (e.g. Values and Attitudes), and sections which were deemed particularly demanding for the respondents.

- **Phase IV: The new Baseline questionnaire (version 3.0.7):**

The questionnaire included in this document is the integral version in the sense that it contains the questions that have been marked for deletion (see explanation above), and some as being optional. They have been kept here in order to have a proper record of the changes introduced and also because they have been used in some countries. To facilitate the use, all amendments have been marked using a colour scheme. The shorter version (3.1.0) excludes the questions marked for deletion

Important remarks and colour-scheme

Optional questions in blue

This questionnaire contains optional questions which can be added to the national surveys or left out. They concern:

- Items related to the Theory of Planned Behaviour for fertility. Specifically, the items FER25, FER26, and FER27 can either be deleted entirely or shortened by deleting items FER25g and FER25h as well as FER26 (items c, d, g and i).
- Items related to the SDG 5.6.1. These are important but sensitive, We encourage their inclusion but countries have to take extra measures in view of their sensitivity. Specifically these are items FER28, FER29 and WEL02a.
- The variable INC04 is also optional. It is a useful multi-item question to capture social exclusion. However, to shorten the questionnaire it can be omitted.

Deleted questions in light grey

This version of the questionnaire contains questions which were asked in some countries but were deleted and will not be asked in subsequent data collections. They are highlighted in light grey.

Filter commands

The questionnaire below is coded using the software BLAISE. We have kept here all the commands including the filters. Some of them may be complex to understand without having access to the full Blaise-coded file. Note for example that an if-command introduces a filter which is applied to the question following the filter. For example, if DEM03 = yes (The respondent was born in this country), DEM04a is asked (see p. 3). The command ENDIF ends the if-command that was introduced before the question. It therefore removes the filter from the subsequent questions.

Item non-response

Note that this version of the questionnaire does not display the answer categories Don't know and Refuse which are included as possible answers in case of the majority of questions.

Green highlights

They refer to external lists (e.g. occupational codes). The Occupation Lists were developed for the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe and in conjunction with the Wage Indicator Survey. These lists are already translated, aligned with ISCO 08 and are available here: <https://www.surveycodings.com/articles/codings/occupation>.

Country-specific questions

The new Baseline questionnaire allows national teams to add if they desire a few questions. Ideally these should appear as a “block” of questions together towards the end of the questionnaire.

Blaise code

The questionnaire has been coded using the Blaise software. All codes and syntax below are Blaise-specific.

About the FER section

Note that the section starts with the variation on fertility intention (FER14). In the past, this section used to start with a question about whether or not the respondent was pregnant (FER01). In this new version of the questionnaire, the information about whether or not the respondent is pregnant is instead a response category in FER14. The information on pregnancy from FER14 is used to construct additional variables (FER01a-c). Later in the questionnaire, there are filters based on these constructed variables, e.g.:

```
(IF (((FER01a = yes)OR(FER01b = yes))OR(FER01c = yes))
```

This filter implies that the subsequent questions are asked to respondents who are either female, below 50 and pregnant (FER01=yes); male or female of all ages with a pregnant, female partner below 50 (FER01b=yes); or men of all ages without a partner or a male partner who are currently expecting a child (FER01c=yes).

A list of further constructed variables can be found in the appendix (p. 94).

Special annotations

At several places in the questionnaire the code “CollectionMember” is used. This refers to the answer the respondent provided in a previous question, for example the name of the partner or the working place.

Response categories that may have to be adjusted by countries

The intent of the new questionnaire is to maximize cross-national comparability. Countries are consequently not allowed to modify questions and answer categories. The only exception are the income question (where the income groups and currency need to be adjusted) and the education questions.

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Expand All

- **respid** (Respondent ID)
To get started, please enter the 9 character access code provided.

XX_____
>AAA-AAA-AAA

STRING

IF (INTERVIEWER)

intid (Interviewer ID)

Interviewer ID

STRING

ENDIF

intro (Intro)

This survey is about family, work and everyday life. Your answers will help us understand the complexities of today's families and the reality of people at different stages of their life. Our aim is to better understand, for example, what influences people's decision to have children or how they share household chores in couples. The results will be used to advise policy-makers on how to improve issues such as work-life balance, social relationships between generations and gender equality. Your participation is voluntary. If you don't want to answer any of the questions as some of them deal with sensitive topics, you are free to skip these at any point by choosing the response option 'refuse'. We will remove all personal identifiers from the data and ensure that your answers are only accessed by authorized and verified researchers for scientific purposes.

Agree to proceed

DEMINT (Demographics Intro) (Empty)

SECTION 1/9: About you...

Let me begin by asking you a few questions about yourself.

DEM01 (Gender)

What is your gender?

Male

Female

DEM02 (Date of birth)

When were you born? [MM/YYYY]

E.g. If you are born in March 1980 please insert 03/1980.

MM/YYYY

>99/9999

IF (DEM02 = RESPONSE)

CHECK: (((len(DEM02) = 6)AND(val(substring(DEM02, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(DEM02, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(DEM02, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)]

ENDIF

DEM03 (Born in country) (Refusal)

Were you born in this country?

Yes

No

IF (DEM03 = yes)

DEM04a (Place of birth) (DontKnow, Refusal)

In which region were you born?

Drenthe

Flevoland

Friesland

Gelderland

Groningen

Limburg

North Brabant

North Holland

Overijssel

South Holland

Utrecht

Zeeland

ENDIF

IF (DEM03 = no)

DEM04b (Country of birth) (DontKnow, Refusal)

In which country were you born?

Please type in (the first letters of) the country and then select the country from the list by clicking on it.

STRING

JOB CODER: CntFile1

DEM05 (Date of immigration) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

When did you first move to this country? [MM/YYYY]

If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

MM/YYYY

Vertical

99/9999

STRING[6]

IF (DEM05 = RESPONSE)

▪

CHECK: (((len(DEM05) = 6)AND(val(substring(DEM05, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(DEM05, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(DEM05, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [*Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)*]

ENDIF

ENDIF

DEM04c (Place of current residence) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

In which region do you currently live?

Drenthe

Flevoland

Friesland

Gelderland

Groningen

Limburg

North Brabant

North Holland

Overijssel

South Holland

Utrecht

Zeeland

DEM06 (Activity status) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Which of the items best describes your current employment status?

If you are evenly split between two or more of these activities, select the one which you feel best describes your current situation.

In education or training

Employed

Self-employed

Helping family member in a family farm or business

Unemployed

Retired

In military or civic service

Taking care of the home or family

On maternity or paternity leave

On parental leave or childcare leave

Ill or disabled for a long time or permanently

Other

DEM07 (Education level [ISCED]) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

What is the highest level of education you have completed?

Please select the education level that corresponds most closely to the highest level of education you have completed.

Early childhood education

Primary education

Lower secondary education

Upper secondary education

Post-secondary non tertiary education

Short cycle tertiary education

Bachelor or equivalent

Master or equivalent

Doctoral or equivalent

IF (NOT(DEM07 = ISCED0))

○

DEM08 (Date education reached) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

When did you reach that level? [MM/YYYY]

If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

MM/YYYY

Vertical

99/9999

STRING[6]

IF (DEM08 = RESPONSE)

▪

CHECK: (((len(DEM08) = 6)AND(val(substring(DEM08, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(DEM08, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(DEM08, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)]

ENDIF

ENDIF

DEMACC (Accommodation Intro) (Empty)

Now I would like to ask you some questions about your accommodation.

DEM09 (Rooms [NUMBER]) (DontKnow, Refusal)

How many rooms do you have?

Exclude kitchen, bathrooms, toilets and rooms used exclusively for business, hallways and utility rooms

NUMBER [0..30]

DEM10 (Date moved in) (DontKnow, Refusal)

When did you start living in this accommodation? [MM/YYYY]

If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

MM/YYYY

Vertical

99/9999

STRING[6]

DEM11 (Housing status) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Does your household own or rent this accommodation or does it come rent free?

Owner

Tenant or subtenant, paying rent

Accommodation is provided rent free

Other

DEM12 (Housing satisfaction) (DontKnow, Refusal)

How satisfied are you with your accommodation?

On a scale from 0 to 10 where 0 means 'not at all satisfied' and 10 means 'completely satisfied' and 5 means 'about average', what number best represents your satisfaction with your accommodation?

NUMBER [0..10]

DEM14 (Internet connection) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Do you have internet at home?

Yes

No

DEM15 (Internet use) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

On a typical day, about how many hours do you spend using the internet on a computer, tablet, mobile or smartphone or other device, whether for work or personal use?

None

Less than 1 hour

1-2 hours

2-4 hours

More than 4 hours

DEM16 (Language at home) (DontKnow, Refusal)

What language do you most frequently speak at home?

Dutch

English

Other

IF (DEM10 = RESPONSE)

CHECK: (((len(DEM10) = 6)AND(val(substring(DEM10, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(DEM10, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(DEM10, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)]

ENDIF

IF (intdate - STRTODATE(01DEM10, ddMMyyyy) < 1460)

DEM17 (Residence 3 years ago) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Where did you live three years ago from today?

The same address as now

Different address, but same town/city/municipality

Different city in the same country

Different country

DEM18 (Reason for moving) (DontKnow, Refusal)

What was the main reason for moving to this address?

Better housing

Better neighbourhood

For family-related reasons

For financial related reasons

For work related reasons

For education related reasons

For health related reasons

To move in with a partner
To start living on my own
Other

ENDIF

DEM19 (Intention to move) (*Refusal*)

Do you intend to move to another **address in 18**; within the next 3 years?

Definitely not
Probably not
Unsure
Probably yes
Definitely yes

DEM20 (Intention to migrate) (*Refusal*)

Do you intend to move to another **country** within the next 3 years?

Definitely not
Probably not
Unsure
Probably yes
Definitely yes

DEM21 (Respondent has a partner) (*Refusal*)

This survey focuses on families and relationships, including both opposite and same sex partnerships. Do you have a partner at the moment?

Yes
No

IF (DEM21 = yes)

○

DEM22a (Place first met current partner) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

How did you and your partner meet?

Through work
In education (School, University, College etc.)
At church or equivalent
Online dating
Other online setting
Vacation or business trip
At a bar, nightclub or dance club
Through a social organization, health club, gym or volunteer group
At a private party or social event
Through friends
Through family
Other

DEM22 (Partners date of birth) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

When was your partner born? [MM/YYYY]

If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

MM/YYYY

Vertical

99/9999

STRING[6]

DEM23 (Gender of partner) (*Refusal*)

Is your partner...

Male
Female

DEM24a (Partner born in country) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Was your partner born in 18;?

Yes
No

IF (DEM22 = RESPONSE)

▪

CHECK: (((len(DEM22) = 6)AND(val(substring(DEM22, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(DEM22, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(DEM22, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [*Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)*]

ENDIF

IF (DEM24a = no)

▪

DEM24b (Partners country of birth) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

In which country was he/she born?

Please type in (the first letters of) the country and then select the country from the list by clicking on it.

STRING

JOB CODER: CntFile2

DEM24e (Partners date of immigration) (*DontKnow, Refusal, NA*)

When did he/she first move to this country? [MM/YYYY]
If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

MM/YYYY
Vertical
99/9999

STRING[6]

IF (DEM24e = RESPONSE)

▪

CHECK: (((len(DEM24e) = 6)AND(val(substring(DEM24e, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(DEM24e, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(DEM24e, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)]

ENDIF

ENDIF

DEM25 (Partners education level [ISCED]) (DontKnow, Refusal)

What is the highest level of education your partner has successfully completed?
Please select the education level that corresponds most closely to the highest level of education he/she has completed.

Early childhood education
Primary education
Lower secondary education
Upper secondary education
Post-secondary non tertiary education
Short cycle tertiary education
Bachelor or equivalent
Master or equivalent
Doctoral or equivalent

DEM26 (Partners employment status) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Which of the items best describes your partner's current employment status?
If he or she is evenly split between two or more of these activities, select the one which you feel best describes his or her current situation.

In education or training
Employed
Self-employed
Helping family member in a family farm or business
Unemployed
Retired
In military or civic service
Taking care of the home or family
On maternity or paternity leave
On parental leave or childcare leave
Ill or disabled for a long time or permanently
Other

DEM27 (Partners limitation of daily activities) (Refusal, DontKnow)

For the past six months at least, to what extent has your partner been limited because of a health problem in activities people usually do? Would you say they have been...

Severely limited
Limited, but not severely
Not limited

DEM28a (Married to partner) (Refusal)

Are you and your partner legally married?

Yes
No

IF (DEM28a = yes)

▪

DEM28b (Date married partner) (DontKnow, Refusal)

When did you marry? [MM/YYYY]
If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

MM/YYYY
Vertical
99/9999

STRING[6]

IF (DEM28b = RESPONSE)

▪

CHECK: (((len(DEM28b) = 6)AND(val(substring(DEM28b, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(DEM28b, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(DEM28b, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)]

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF (DEM28a = no)

▪

DEM29a (Registered partnership) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Are you and your partner living in a registered partnership?

Yes

No

IF (DEM29a = yes)

▪

DEM29b (Date partnership registered) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

When did you register your partnership? [MM/YYYY]

If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

MM/YYYY

Vertical

99/9999

STRING[6]

IF (DEM29b = RESPONSE)

▪

CHECK: (((len(DEM29b) = 6)AND(val(substring(DEM29b, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(DEM29b, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(DEM29b, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)]

ENDIF

ENDIF

ENDIF

DEM30a (Living with partner) (*Refusal*)

Does your partner live with you in the same household?

Yes

No

IF (DEM30a = yes)

▪

DEM30b (Date started living with partner) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

When did you and he/she first start living together? [MM/YYYY]

If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

MM/YYYY

Vertical

99/9999

STRING[6]

IF (DEM30b = RESPONSE)

▪

CHECK: (((len(DEM30b) = 6)AND(val(substring(DEM30b, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(DEM30b, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(DEM30b, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)]

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF (DEM30a = no)

▪

DEM30c (Intention to start cohabiting) (*Refusal*)

Do you intend to start living with your partner during the next 3 years?

Definitely not

Probably not

Unsure

Probably yes

Definitely yes

ENDIF

IF (((DEM30c = unsure)OR(DEM30c = probyes))OR(DEM30c = defyes))AND(DEM28a = no))

▪

DEM30d (Intention to cohabit or marry) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Do you intend to just live together or will you get married straight away?

Cohabit only

Marry straight away

Cohabit at first

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF (DEM28a = no)

○

DEM28c (Intention to marry) (*Refusal*)

Do you intend to marry your partner during the next 3 years?

Definitely not

Probably not

Unsure

Probably yes
Definitely yes

ENDIF
IF (DEM21 = yes)

- - IF (DEM30a = no)
 - - DEM31** (Date relationship started) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)
When did this relationship start? [MM/YYYY]
If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.
MM/YYYY
Vertical
99/9999
STRING[6]
 - DEM32a** (Reason for living apart) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)
Are you living apart because you and/or your partner want to or because circumstances prevent you from living together?
I want to live apart
We both want to live apart
Partner wants to live apart
We are constrained by circumstances
 - IF (DEM31 = RESPONSE)
 - - CHECK:** (((len(DEM31) = 6)AND(val(substring(DEM31, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(DEM31, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(DEM31, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [*Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)*]
 - ENDIF
IF ((DEM32a = me)OR(DEM32a = both))
 - - DEM32b** (Rs reason for living apart) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)
Why do you (Respondent) want to live apart? Please choose the most important reason.
For financial reasons
To maintain independence
Because of children
Not yet ready for living together
Other
 - ENDIF
IF ((DEM32a = both)OR(DEM32a = partner))
 - - DEM32c** (Partners reason for living apart) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)
Why does your partner want to live apart? Please choose the most important reason.
For financial reasons
To maintain independence
Because of children
Not yet ready for living together
Other
 - ENDIF
IF (DEM32a = circumstance)
 - - DEM32d** (Circumstances for living apart) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)
By which circumstances? Please choose the most important circumstances.
Work circumstances
Financial circumstances
Housing circumstances
Legal circumstances
Family circumstances
Other
 - ENDIF
IF (DEM28a = no)
 - - DEM33** (Ever married to current partner) (*Refusal*)
Have you ever been legally married to him/her?
Yes
No
 - IF (DEM33 = yes)
 -

DEM33a (Date married current partner) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)
When did you marry? [MM/YYYY]
If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.
MM/YYYY
Vertical
99/9999
STRING[6]

DEM34 (Date divorced current partner) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)
When did you get a divorce? [MM/YYYY]
If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.
MM/YYYY
Vertical
99/9999
STRING[6]

IF (DEM33a = RESPONSE)

▪

CHECK: (((len(DEM33a) = 6)AND(val(substring(DEM33a, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(DEM33a, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(DEM33a, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [*Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)*]

ENDIF

IF (DEM34 = RESPONSE)

▪

CHECK: (((len(DEM34) = 6)AND(val(substring(DEM34, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(DEM34, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(DEM34, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [*Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)*]

ENDIF

ENDIF

ENDIF

DEM35 (Residence of current partner [MIN]) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)
How long does it take to get from your home to where he/she is living at present?
Please provide an answer in hours and minutes [HH:MM]
--:--
Vertical
STRING[5]

DEM36a (Meetings non-resident partner [FREQ]) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)
How often do you meet with him/her in person?
NUMBER [0..365]

IF (NOT((DEM36a = Refusal)OR(DEM36a = DontKnow)))

▪

DEM36au (Meetings non-resident partner [UNIT]) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)
times a...
Week
Month
Year

ENDIF

DEM36b (Contact non-resident partner [FREQ]) (*Never, DontKnow, Refusal*)
How often do you have contact with him/her by phone, mail, email or any other electronic means?
NUMBER [0..365]

IF (NOT((DEM36b = never)OR(DEM36b = Refusal))OR(DEM36b = DontKnow)))

▪

DEM36bu (Contact non-resident partner [UNIT]) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)
times a...
Week
Month
Year

ENDIF

ENDIF

DEM37 (Relationship satisfaction) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)
How satisfied are you with your relationship with your partner?
On a scale from 0 to 10 where 0 means 'not at all satisfied' and 10 means 'completely satisfied' and 5 means 'about average', what number best represents your satisfaction with your relationship?
NUMBER [0..10]

DEM38 (Couple Disagreements: Intro) (*Empty*)
Within the last 12 months, how often did you and your partner have disagreement about...

DEM38a (Couple Disagr: Household chores) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

...household chores?

Never
Seldom
Sometimes
Frequently
Very frequently

DEM38b (Couple Disagr: Money) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

...money?

Never
Seldom
Sometimes
Frequently
Very frequently

DEM38c (Couple Disagr: Leisure time) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

...use of leisure time?

Never
Seldom
Sometimes
Frequently
Very frequently

DEM38d (Couple Disagr: Relationship with friends) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

...relations with friends?

Never
Seldom
Sometimes
Frequently
Very frequently

DEM38e (Couple Disagr: Relation parents(in law)) (*DontKnow, Refusal, NA*)

...relations with parents?

Never
Seldom
Sometimes
Frequently
Very frequently

DEM38f (Couple Disagr: Having children) (*DontKnow, Refusal, NA*)

...having children?

Never
Seldom
Sometimes
Frequently
Very frequently

DEM38g (Couple Disagr: Child raising) (*DontKnow, Refusal, NA*)

...child raising issues?

Never
Seldom
Sometimes
Frequently
Very frequently

DEM39 (Disagreement Resolution: Intro) (*Empty*)

Couples deal with serious disagreements in various ways. When you have a serious disagreement with your partner, how often do you....

DEM39a (Disagr Resolution: Giving in) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

...avoid discussion by giving in?

Never
Seldom
Sometimes
Frequently
Very frequently

DEM39b (Disagr Resolution: Discuss calmly) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

...discuss your disagreement calmly?

Never
Seldom
Sometimes
Frequently
Very frequently

DEM39c (Disagr Resolution: Argue and shout) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

...argue heatedly or shout?

Never
Seldom
Sometimes

Frequently
Very frequently

DEM39d (Disagr Resolution: Refuse to talk) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)
...refuse to talk about it?

Never
Seldom
Sometimes
Frequently
Very frequently

DEM40 (Considered break Up) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Even people who get along well with their partners sometimes wonder whether their marriage or partnership will work. Over the past 12 months, have you thought about breaking up your relationship?

Yes
No

DEM41 (Biological children with partner) (*Refusal*)

Do you and your partner have children together? Please consider only the children of whom you are the biological parents as well as children born via donor conception or surrogacy.

Yes
No

IF (DEM41 = yes)

▪

DEM42 (Biological childr. with partner [NUMBER]) (*Refusal*)

How many biological children have you had together (including children born via donor conception or surrogacy)?

NUMBER [0..20]

ENDIF

DEM43 (Adopted children with partner) (*Refusal*)

Have you and your partner adopted children together?

Yes
No

IF (DEM43 = yes)

▪

DEM44 (Adopted children with partner [NUMBER]) (*Refusal*)

How many children have you adopted with your partner?

NUMBER [0..20]

ENDIF

DEM45 (Partners children) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Has your partner had any children of her/his own?

Yes
No

IF (DEM45 = yes)

▪

DEM46 (Partners children [NUMBER]) (*Refusal*)

How many children has she/he had without you?

NUMBER [0..20]

ENDIF

ENDIF

LHIINT (Life History Intro) (*Empty*)

SECTION 2/9: About your relationships and children...

Now we would like to ask some questions about previous relationships and the children that you might have had. It is really important for us to understand what and when things happened so that we can better understand your story.

LHI01 (Lived ever with a partner) (*Refusal*)

Not including any current partnership, have you ever before lived with someone as a couple or have you ever been married?

Yes
No

IF (LHI01 = yes)

○

LHI02 (Previous partnerships [NUMBER]) (*Refusal*)

Not including your current relationship, how many partnerships did you have where you lived together?

NUMBER [0..20]

IF (NOT(LHI02 = Refusal))

▪

LHI03 (Partner name) (*Empty*)

To help us with guiding you through the next few questions, please provide the names of all these previous partners.
You can use pseudonyms or descriptions instead of names if you prefer and this information will be deleted at the end of the interview.

ENDIF

LOOP I := 1 TO LHI02

▪

LHI03_[I] (Partner name)

To help us with guiding you through the next few questions, please provide the names of all these previous partners, starting with the first one.

You can use pseudonyms or descriptions if you prefer and this information will be deleted at the end of the interview.

Name of previous partner

ENDLOOP

LOOP I := 1 TO LHI02

▪

LHI04a_[I] (Place first met partner) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

How did you and **CollectionMember** meet?

Through work

In education (School, University, College etc.)

At church or equivalent

Online dating

Other online setting

Vacation or business trip

At a bar, nightclub or dance club

Through a social organization, health club, gym or volunteer group

At a private party or social event

Through friends

Through family

Other

LHI04_[I] (Date started cohabiting partner) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

When did you start living together with **CollectionMember**? [MM/YYYY]

If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

MM/YYYY

Vertical

99/9999

STRING[6]

LHI05a_[I] (Married to partner) (*Refusal*)

Were you and **CollectionMember** legally married?

Yes

No

IF (LHI04_ = RESPONSE)

▪

CHECK: (((len(LHI04_) = 6)AND(val(substring(LHI04_, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(LHI04_, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(LHI04_, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [*Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)*]

ENDIF

IF (LHI05a_ = yes)

▪

LHI05b_[I] (Date married partner) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

When did you marry **CollectionMember**? [MM/YYYY]

If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

MM/YYYY

Vertical

99/9999

STRING[6]

IF (LHI05b_ = RESPONSE)

▪

CHECK: (((len(LHI05b_) = 6)AND(val(substring(LHI05b_, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(LHI05b_, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(LHI05b_, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [*Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)*]

ENDIF

ENDIF

LHI06_[I] (Partner date of birth) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

When was **CollectionMember** born? [MM/YYYY]

If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

MM/YYYY

Vertical

99/9999

STRING[6]

LHI07_[I] (Children with partner) (*Refusal*)

Have you and **CollectionMember** had children together? Please consider only the children of whom you are the biological parents as well as children born via donor conception or surrogacy.

Yes

No

IF (LHI06_ = RESPONSE)

▪

CHECK: (((len(LHI06_) = 6)AND(val(substring(LHI06_, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(LHI06_, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(LHI06_, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [*Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)*]

ENDIF

IF (LHI07_ = yes)

▪

LHI08_[I] (Children with partner [NUMBER]) (*Refusal*)

How many biological children have you had together(including children born via donor conception or surrogacy)?

ENDIF

LHI09_[I] (Adopted children with partner) (*Refusal*)

Have you and **CollectionMember** adopted any children?

Yes

No

IF (LHI09_ = yes)

▪

LHI10_[I] (Adopted children with partner [NUMBER]) (*Refusal*)

How many children have you and **CollectionMember** adopted?

ENDIF

LHI11_[I] (Step children with partner) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

When you started living together had **CollectionMember** already had children of his or her own?

Yes

No

IF (LHI11_ = yes)

▪

LHI12_[I] (Step children with partner [NUMBER]) (*Refusal*)

How many children did **CollectionMember** have?

ENDIF

LHI13_[I] (How partnership ended) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

How did this partnership end?

Broke up

Partner passed away

LHI14_[I] (Date partnership ended) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

When did that happen? [MM/YYYY]

If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

MM/YYYY

Vertical

99/9999

STRING[6]

IF (LHI14_ = RESPONSE)

▪

CHECK: (((len(LHI14_) = 6)AND(val(substring(LHI14_, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(LHI14_, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(LHI14_, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [*Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)*]

ENDIF

IF ((LHI05a_ = yes)AND(LHI13_ = brokeup))

▪

LHI15a_[I] (Divorce partner) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Did you and **CollectionMember** get divorced?

Yes

No

IF (LHI15a_ = yes)

▪

LHI15b_[I] (Date divorce partner) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

When did you get divorced? [MM/YYYY]

If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

MM/YYYY

```

Vertical
99/9999
STRING[6]
LHI16_[I] (Who started divorce with Partner) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Who started the legal process of divorce?
Me/I
Me and partner together
Partner
IF (LHI15b_ = RESPONSE)
  ▪ 
    CHECK: (((len(LHI15b_) = 6)AND(val(substring(LHI15b_, 1,
    2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(LHI15b_, 3, 4)) >
    1900))AND(val(substring(LHI15b_, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [Please enter
    a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)]
ENDIF
ENDIF
LHI17_[I] (Same gender partner) (Refusal)
Our survey also includes same sex partnerships. Was CollectionMember the same
sex as you?
Yes
No
ENDLOOP
ENDIF
LHI18 (Children outside cohabitation) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Have you had any children with someone you have never lived with?
Yes
No
IF (LHI18 = yes)
  ○ 
    LHI19 (Children outside cohabitation [NUMBER]) (Refusal)
    How many children have you had with someone you never lived with?
    NUMBER [0..10]
ENDIF
LHI20 (Child count verification) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Based on the information you have provided you had 0; biological children, 0; adopted children
and 0; stepchildren. Is this correct?
Please also include children who passed away.
A stepchild is a child of a partner or an ex-partner from a relationship they had before you.
Yes
No
IF (LHI20 = no)
  ○ 
    LHI21 (Biological children [NUMBER]) (Refusal)
    How many biological children have you had in total (including children born via donor con-
    ception or surrogacy)?
    NUMBER [0..20]
    LHI22 (Stepchildren [NUMBER]) (Refusal)
    How many step children do you have in total?
    NUMBER [0..20]
    LHI23 (Adopted children [NUMBER]) (Refusal)
    How many adopted children do you have in total?
    NUMBER [0..20]
ENDIF
IF (totalchildren > 0)
  ○ 
    LHI24 (Child name) (Empty)
    To help us with guiding you through the next few questions, please provide the names of
    all these children, starting with the oldest.
    You can use pseudonyms or descriptions (e.g. oldest daughter) if you prefer and this infor-
    mation will be deleted at the end of the interview.
    Name of Child
    LOOP I := 1 TO totalchildren
      ▪ 
        LHI24_[I] (Child name)
        To help us with guiding you through the next few questions, please provide the
        names of all these children, starting with the oldest.
        You can use pseudonyms or descriptions (e.g. oldest daughter) if you prefer and
        this information will be deleted at the end of the interview.
        Name of Child

```

```

ENDLOOP
LOOP I := 1 TO totalchildren
  ■ 
  LHI25_[I] (Child alive) (DontKnow, Refusal)
  Is CollectionMember still alive?
  Yes
  No
  LHI26_[I] (Child type) (Refusal, NA)
  Please indicate if CollectionMember is...
  Biological child
  Adopted child
  Step child
  LHI27_[I] (Parent of child) (DontKnow, Refusal, Empty)
  Who is the (other) parent of CollectionMember?
  Current partner
  ^BLIFEHIST.LHI03_;
  ^BLIFEHIST.LHI03_;
  ^BLIFEHIST.LHI03_;
  ^BLIFEHIST.LHI03_;
  ^BLIFEHIST.LHI03_;
  ^BLIFEHIST.LHI03_;
  ^BLIFEHIST.LHI03_;
  Other
  LHI28_[I] (Gender of child) (Refusal)
  Is CollectionMember ...
  Male
  Female
  LHI29_[I] (Child date of birth) (DontKnow, Refusal)
  When was CollectionMember born? [MM/YYYY]
  If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.
  MM/YYYY
  Vertical
  99/9999
  STRING[6]
  IF (LHI29_ = RESPONSE)
    ■ 
    CHECK: (((len(LHI29_) = 6)AND(val(substring(LHI29_, 1, 2)) <=
    12))AND(val(substring(LHI29_, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(LHI29_, 3,
    4)) < 2023)) [Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)]
  ENDIF
  IF (LHI25_ = no)
    ■ 
    LHI30_[I] (Child date of death) (DontKnow, Refusal)
    When did CollectionMember pass away? [MM/YYYY]
    If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.
    MM/YYYY
    Vertical
    99/9999
    STRING[6]
    IF (LHI30_ = RESPONSE)
      ■ 
      CHECK: (((len(LHI30_) = 6)AND(val(substring(LHI30_, 1, 2)) <=
      12))AND(val(substring(LHI30_, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(sub-
      string(LHI30_, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a
      year (e.g. 1990)]
    ENDIF
  ENDIF
  IF (LHI25_ = yes)
    ■ 
    LHI31_[I] (Child lives in same HH) (Refusal)
    Is CollectionMember currently living in the same household with you?
    Yes, always
    Yes, most of the time
    Yes, some of the time
    No, never
    IF ((NOT(LHI31_ = yesa))AND(childage_ < 18))
      ■ 
      LHI32_[I] (Child usual residency) (DontKnow, Refusal)
      Where does the child stay the rest of the time?

```

With biological parent
With biological parent and his/her partner
With (a) grandparent(s)
With other relative(s)
With adoptive parent(s)
With foster parent(s)
Boarding school
Orphanage
In a youth home
Other

LHI33_[I] (Looking after child [FREQ]) (*never, DontKnow, Refusal*)

How often do you look after **CollectionMember**?

Vertical

IF (NOT(((LHI33_ = never)OR(LHI33_ = DontKnow))OR(LHI33_ = Refusal)))

▪

LHI33u_[I] (Looking after child [UNIT]) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

times a...

Week

Month

Year

ENDIF

LHI34_[I] (Overnight stay of child [FREQ]) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

How many nights does **CollectionMember** spend in your household on average per week?

ENDIF

IF (childage_ > 14)

▪

LHI35_[I] (Activity status of child) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Which of the items best describes what **CollectionMember** is mainly doing at present?

In education or training

Employed

Self-employed

Helping family member in a family farm or business

Unemployed

Retired

In military or civic service

Taking care of the home or family

On maternity or paternity leave

On parental leave or childcare leave

Ill or disabled for a long time or permanently

Other

ENDIF

IF (((LHI31_ = yesa)OR(LHI31_ = yesm))OR(LHI31_ = yess))

▪

LHI36_[I] (Limitation or disability of child) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

For the past six months at least, to what extent has **CollectionMember** been limited because of a health problem in activities people usually do? Would you say they have been...

Severely limited

Limited, but not severely

Not limited

LHI37_[I] (Child health) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

How is **CollectionMember**'s health in general?

Very good

Good

Fair

Bad

Very bad

ENDIF

IF (LHI31_ = no)

▪

LHI38_[I] (Child ever lived in household) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Has **CollectionMember** ever lived with you in the same household for more than 3 months?

Yes

No

IF (childage_ > 14)

▪

LHI39a_[I] (Meeting with child [FREQ]) (*Never, DontKnow, Refusal*)

How often do you meet with **CollectionMember** in person?
IF (NOT(((LHI39a_ = never)OR(LHI39a_ = DontKnow))OR(LHI39a_ = Refusal)))

LHI39au_[I] (Meeting with child [UNIT]) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

times a...

Week

Month

Year

ENDIF

LHI39b_[I] (Contact with child [FREQ]) (*Never, DontKnow, Refusal*)

How often do you have contact with **CollectionMember** by phone, mail, email or any other electronic means?

IF (NOT(((LHI39b_ = never)OR(LHI39b_ = DontKnow))OR(LHI39b_ = Refusal)))

LHI39bu_[I] (Contact with child [UNIT]) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

times a...

Week

Month

Year

ENDIF

ENDIF

LHI40_[I] (Child home [MIN]) (*DontKnow, Refusal, NA*)

How long does it take to get from your home to where **CollectionMember** is living at present?

Please provide an answer in hours and minutes [HH:MM]<\\I>

--:--

Vertical

STRING[5]

ENDIF

LHI41_[I] (Relationship satisfaction with child) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

How satisfied are you with your relationship with **CollectionMember**?

On a scale from 0 to 10 where 0 means 'not at all satisfied' and 10 means 'completely satisfied' and 5 means 'about average', what number best represents your satisfaction with your relationship?

ENDIF

ENDLOOP

ENDIF

FERINT (Fertility Intro) (Empty)

SECTION 3/9: About sexual health and fertility...

This section includes some sensitive questions. Please remember that your answers will be treated in the strictest confidence.

IF (((((asex = female)AND(age < 50))OR(((asex = male)AND(partnerage < 50))AND(BDEMOGRAPHICS.DEM23 = female)))OR((asex = male)AND(NOT(BDEMOGRAPHICS.DEM23 = female))))OR(((asex = female)AND(BDEMOGRAPHICS.DEM23 = female))AND(partnerage < 50)))

FER14 (Intention to have a child in next 3y) (*Refusal*)

Do you intend to have a/another child during the next three years? Please take into account only biological children.

Definitely not

Probably not

Unsure

Probably yes

Definitely yes

Currently expecting a child

IF (NOT(FER14 = pregnant))

FER15 (Intention to have a child at all) (*Refusal*)

Supposing you do not have a/another child during the next three years, do you intend to have any (more) children at all?

Definitely not

Probably not

Unsure
Probably yes
Definitely yes

ENDIF

IF (NOT(FER15 = defno))

▪

FER16a (Total number of children intended) (DontKnow, Refusal)

How many more children - including biological and adoptive children - do you intend to have overall? [Not including existing children]

NUMBER [0..10]

ENDIF

FER25 (Child impact intro) (Empty)

Even though you might not intend to have a/another child, we would still want your opinion about this possibility. Suppose that during the next 3 years you were to have a/another child. I would like you to tell me what effect you think this would have on various aspects of your life

FER25a (Child Impact: Do what you want) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

the possibility to do what you want

Much better

Better

Neither better nor worse

Worse

Much worse

FER25b (Child Impact: Money to spend) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

the amount of money you can spend

Much better

Better

Neither better nor worse

Worse

Much worse

FER25c (Child Impact: Realize other goals) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

the possibility to realize other goals in life

Much better

Better

Neither better nor worse

Worse

Much worse

FER25d (Child Impact: Joy from life) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

the joy and satisfaction you get from life

Much better

Better

Neither better nor worse

Worse

Much worse

FER25e (Child Impact: Employment opportunities) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

your employment opportunities

Much better

Better

Neither better nor worse

Worse

Much worse

FER25f (Child Impact: Partners work opportunity) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

your partner's employment opportunities

Much better

Better

Neither better nor worse

Worse

Much worse

FER25g (Child Impact: Security in old age) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

the care and security you may get in old age

Much better

Better

Neither better nor worse

Worse

Much worse

FER25h (Child Impact: Closeness with spouse) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

the closeness between you and your partner

Much better

Better

Neither better nor worse

Worse
Much worse

FER26 (Decision to have child Intro) (Empty)

The next statements are about conditions that might need to be fulfilled before people have a/another child.

Regardless if you plan to have a child or not, I would like to ask you whether you believe these conditions will be fulfilled, for you, in the next three years.

FER26a (Intend to have child: Financial) (Refusal, NA)

I will be able to financially afford to have a/another child

Definitely not
Probably not
Unsure
Probably yes
Definitely yes

FER26b (Intend to have child: Housing) (Refusal, NA)

I will have access to suitable housing to allow me to have a/another child

Definitely not
Probably not
Unsure
Probably yes
Definitely yes

FER26c (Intend to have child: Health) (Refusal, NA)

I will be healthy enough to have a/another child

Definitely not
Probably not
Unsure
Probably yes
Definitely yes

FER26d (Intend to have child: Feel ready) (Refusal, NA)

I will feel ready to have a/another child

Definitely not
Probably not
Unsure
Probably yes
Definitely yes

FER26e (Intend to have child: Suitable partner) (Refusal, NA)

I will have a suitable partner with whom to have a/another child

Definitely not
Probably not
Unsure
Probably yes
Definitely yes

FER26f (Intend to have child: Work fam. balance) (Refusal, NA)

I will be able to balance my work and family life if I have a/another child

Definitely not
Probably not
Unsure
Probably yes
Definitely yes

IF (BDEMOGRAPHICS.DEM01 = male)

▪

FER26g (Intend to have child: Partners health) (Refusal, NA)

My partner will be healthy enough to have a/another child

Definitely not
Probably not
Unsure
Probably yes
Definitely yes

ENDIF

FER26h (Intend to have child: Childcare) (Refusal, NA)

I will have access to satisfactory childcare if I have a/another child

Definitely not
Probably not
Unsure
Probably yes
Definitely yes

FER26i (Intend to have child: Leave) (Refusal, NA)

I will have access to sufficient parental leave if I have a/another child

Definitely not
Probably not
Unsure

Probably yes
Definitely yes

FER27 (Further Children Opinion Intro) (Empty)

The next statements are about what other people might think about you having a/another child during the next 3 years.

Please indicate to what extent you agree or disagree with these statements.

FER27a (Further Children Opinions: Friends) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

Most of my friends think I should have a/another child

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

FER27b (Further Children Opinions: Parents) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

My parents think I should have a/another child

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

IF (BDEMOGRAPHICS.DEM21 = yes)

▪

FER27c (Further Children Opinions: Partner) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

My partner thinks we should have a/another child

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

ENDIF

FER16c (General ideal family size) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Generally speaking, what do you think is the ideal number of children for a family?

NUMBER [0..10]

FER16b (Personal ideal family size) (DontKnow, Refusal)

For you personally, what would be the ideal number of children you would like to have or would have liked to have had?

NUMBER [0..10]

IF (((FER15 = probyes)OR(FER15 = defyes))OR(FER15 = unsure))

▪

FER17 (Child gender preference) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Would you prefer your first/next child to be a boy or a girl?

Boy

Girl

It does not matter

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF (((FER01a = yes)OR(FER01b = yes))OR(FER01c = yes))

○

FER02 (Due date) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Earlier you mentioned that you or your partner were expecting a child. When is the child expected to be born? [MM/YYYY]

If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

MM/YYYY

Vertical

99/9999

STRING[6]

FER03 (Pregnancy intended) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Just before this pregnancy began, did you yourself intend to have a/another baby at some time?

Yes

No

Didn't mind either way

IF (FER02 = RESPONSE)

▪

CHECK: (((len(FER02) = 6)AND(val(substring(FER02, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(FER02, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(FER02, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)]

ENDIF

IF (NOT(FER03 = no))

▪

FER04 (Pregnancy timing (current)) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Did this pregnancy occur sooner than you wanted, later than you wanted, or at about the right time?

Sooner

Later

About the right time

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF (((age < 50)AND(NOT(FER01a = yes)))AND(NOT(FER01b = yes)))AND(hasbiolchildunder15 = yes))

○ **FER04b** (Last pregnancy intended) (DontKnow, Refusal)

When your youngest child was conceived, did you yourself intend to have a/another baby?

Yes

No

Didn't mind either way

IF (NOT(FER04b = no))

▪

▪ **FER04c** (Pregnancy timing (previous)) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Did this pregnancy occur sooner than you wanted, later than you wanted, or at about the right time?

Sooner

Later

About the right time

ENDIF

ENDIF

FER04d (Problems conceiving) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Was there ever a time when you and a partner were trying to get pregnant but did not conceive within at least 12 months?

Yes

No

IF ((asex = female)AND(hasbiolchildunder15 = yes))

○

○ **FER04e** (Post-partum amenorrhea) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Has your menstrual cycle been restored since your last pregnancy?

Yes

No

ENDIF

IF (age < 50)

○

IF (((NOT(FER01a = yes))AND(NOT(FER01b = yes)))AND(NOT(FER01c = yes)))

▪

▪ **FER05** (Able to have children) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Some people are not physically able to have children. As far as you know, is it physically possible for you, yourself, to have a/another baby?

Definitely not

Probably Not

Probably yes

Definitely yes

IF ((FER05 = defnot)OR(FER05 = probnot))

▪

▪ **FER06** (Sterilized) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Have you been sterilised or have you had an operation that makes it impossible for you to have a child/ more children?

Yes

No

IF (NOT(FER06 = yes))

▪

▪ **FER07_** (Infertility diagnosis) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Have you been diagnosed with anything that might explain why you might not be able to have (more) children? Please choose all that apply to you.

SET OF Endometriosis

Adhesions

Blocked tubes

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS)

Pelvic inflammatory disease

No/irregular ovulation

Poor sperm count/quality

Uterine fibroids
 No cause was found
 None of the above

ENDIF
 ENDIF
 IF (BDEMOGRAPHICS.DEM21 = yes)

- FER08** (Partner able to have children) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 As far as you know, is it physically possible for your current partner to have a child of his/her own if he/she wanted to?
 Definitely not
 Probably Not
 Probably yes
 Definitely yes
 IF ((FER08 = defnot)OR(FER08 = probnot))
 - FER09** (Partner sterilized) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 Has your partner ever been sterilized or had an operation that makes it impossible for him/her to have a child/ more children?
 Yes
 No

ENDIF
 ENDIF
 IF (((NOT((BDEMOGRAPHICS.DEM01 = male)AND(BDEMOGRAPHICS.DEM23 = male)))AND(NOT((BDEMOGRAPHICS.DEM01 = male)AND(BDEMOGRAPHICS.DEM21 = no))))AND(NOT(((FER05 = defnot)OR(FER06 = yes))AND(BDEMOGRAPHICS.DEM01 = female))))

- FER10a** (Trying to get pregnant) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 Are you or your current partner trying to get pregnant?
 Yes
 No
 IF (FER10a = yes)
 - FER10b** (Date started trying to get pregnant) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 When did you or your current partner start trying to get pregnant?
 [MM/YYYY]
 If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.
 MM/YYYY
 Vertical
 99/9999
 STRING[6]
 IF (FER10b = RESPONSE)
 - CHECK:** (((len(FER10b) = 6)AND(val(substring(FER10b, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(FER10b, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(FER10b, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)]

ENDIF
 ENDIF
 ENDIF
 ENDIF
FER11_ (Infertility treatments) (Nota, DontKnow, Refusal)
 Have you or your partner ever done any of these things to help you get pregnant? Please select all of the things you have been doing.
 SET OF Receiving medication
 Methods for ascertaining timing of ovulation
 In vitro fertilisation (IVF) or micro-fertilisation (ICSI)
 Surgery
 Artificial insemination
 Consulted a physician
 Other medical treatment
 IF ((NOT(FER01a = yes))AND(NOT(FER01b = yes)))

- FER12_** (Contraceptive use) (DontKnow, Refusal, Empty)
 Are you or your partner using or doing any of these things to prevent pregnancy at this time? Please name all of the things you use or do.

SET OF Condom
Pills
Intra uterine device (coil, loop)
Diaphragm/ cervical cap
Foam/cream/jelly/suppository
Injectables (e.g. Depo Provera)
Implants (e.g. Norplant)
Determining fertile days by monitoring hormone changes in urine (e.g. Persona)
Hormonal emergency contraception afterwards (morning after pill)
Withdrawal
Safe period method (rhythm)
Vaginal ring
Female condom
Other method
Not using any method

ENDIF

IF (haspartner = yes)

▪

FER29 (Contraception autonomy) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

Who usually decides on using contraception?

Always me

Usually me

Equally me and partner

Usually partner

Always partner

Always or usually someone else

ENDIF

FER13 (Intercourse in last 4 weeks) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Did you have sexual intercourse in the past 4 weeks?

Yes

No

IF (haspartner = yes)

▪

FER28 (Sexual autonomy) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

Can you say no to your partner if you do not want to have sexual intercourse?

Yes

No

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF (asex = female)

○

FER21 (Age first menstruation) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

How old were you when your menstruation started?

NUMBER [0..50]

FER24 (Age starting menopause) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

How old were you when you started menopause? If you have not started menopause, select not applicable

NUMBER [0..79]

ENDIF

IF (asex = male)

○

FER22 (Age voice breaking) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

How old were you when your voice began to deepen?

NUMBER [0..50]

ENDIF

FER23 (Age first intercourse) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

How old were you when you first had sexual intercourse? If you have not had sexual intercourse, select not applicable

NUMBER [0..50]

IF (((((asex = female)AND(age < 50))OR(((asex = male)AND(partnerage < 50))AND(BDEMOGRAPHICS.DEM23 = female)))OR((asex = male)AND(NOT(BDEMOGRAPHICS.DEM23 = female))))OR(((asex = female)AND(BDEMOGRAPHICS.DEM23 = female))AND(partnerage < 50)))

○

FER30 (Miller Intro) (Empty)

There are many reasons why people choose to have children or not. Please indicate how important the following reasons are to you personally.

FER30a (JoysPBI) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Strong maternal / paternal instincts

Not important at all
Rather unimportant
Neither important nor unimportant
Rather important
Very important

FER30b (TradPar1) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Having a child makes the parents' relationship stronger

Not important at all
Rather unimportant
Neither important nor unimportant
Rather important
Very important

FER30c (TradPar2) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Having a child means parents fulfil their religious values about family life

Not important at all
Rather unimportant
Neither important nor unimportant
Rather important
Very important

FER30d (FeelNaC) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Having a child brings lifelong happiness

Not important at all
Rather unimportant
Neither important nor unimportant
Rather important
Very important

FER30e (InstVoC) (DontKnow, Refusal)

The child is a confirmation of the parent's fertility

Not important at all
Rather unimportant
Neither important nor unimportant
Rather important
Very important

FER30f (SatChR) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Guiding and teaching a child is greatly satisfying to parents

Not important at all
Rather unimportant
Neither important nor unimportant
Rather important
Very important

FER30_2 (Miller Addit) (Empty)

On this page you will find more reasons. Please indicate how important each of them are to you personally.

FER30g (DiscPaC) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Pregnancy and delivery are strenuous for women

Not important at all
Rather unimportant
Neither important nor unimportant
Rather important
Very important

FER30h (FaWPar) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Being responsible for your child is very difficult

Not important at all
Rather unimportant
Neither important nor unimportant
Rather important
Very important

FER30i (NegChC1) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Raising a child limits parents' freedom to do other things

Not important at all
Rather unimportant
Neither important nor unimportant
Rather important
Very important

FER30j (NegChC2) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Raising a child is a great burden on parents' time and energy

Not important at all
Rather unimportant
Neither important nor unimportant
Rather important
Very important

FER30k (NegChC3) (DontKnow, Refusal)

It is difficult to combine work and childrearing
Not important at all
Rather unimportant
Neither important nor unimportant
Rather important
Very important

FER30I (ParStr) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Having a child adds strain to the relationship between the parents
Not important at all
Rather unimportant
Neither important nor unimportant
Rather important
Very important

ENDIF

HHDINT (HH Grid Intro) (Empty)

SECTION 4/9: About your household...

The next questions are about all other persons who live in your household.

HHD01a (Other HH Members) (Refusal)

Does anybody else live with you in this household (apart from your partner and biological, adopted or stepchildren) ?

Please also consider individuals who are household members only part of the time.

Yes

No

IF (HHD01a = yes)

○

○ **HHD01b** (Other HH members [NUMBER]) (DontKnow, Refusal)

How many other people live in your household (apart from your partner and biological, adopted or stepchildren)?

NUMBER [0..20]

ENDIF

IF ((HHD01a = yes)AND(NOT((HHD01b = DontKnow)OR(HHD01b = Refusal))))

○

○ **HHD02** (Name of HH Member) (Empty)

To help us with guiding you through the next few questions, please provide the names of all these people.

You can use pseudonyms or descriptions if you prefer and this information will be deleted at the end of the interview.

Name of Other Household Member

LOOP I := 1 TO HHD01b

▪

HHD02_[I] (Name of HH member)

To help us with guiding you through the next few questions, please provide the names of all these people.

You can use pseudonyms or descriptions if you prefer and this information will be deleted at the end of the interview.

Name of Other Household Member

ENDLOOP

LOOP I := 1 TO HHD01b

▪

HHD03_[I] (Temporary away HH member) (DontKnow, Refusal)

*Is **CollectionMember** away on business, at school, at boarding school, at university, in hospital or somewhere else?*

Yes

No

HHD04_[I] (Relationship type to HH member) (DontKnow, Refusal)

*What is **CollectionMember** relationship to you?*

Biological parent

Step, adoptive or foster parent

Partner's biological parent

Partner's step, adoptive or foster parent

Foster child

Grand or great-grandchild (my own or partner's)

Grand or great-grandparent (my own or partner's)

Brother or sister

Partner's brother or sister

Child's partner

Other relative of mine

Other relative of partner

Friend, acquaintance, colleague
Other nonrelative

HHD05_[I] (Sex of HH member) (Refusal)

Is **CollectionMember** ...

Male

Female

HHD06_[I] (HH member date of birth) (DontKnow, Refusal)

What is **CollectionMember** date of birth? [MM/YYYY]

If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

MM/YYYY

Vertical

99/9999

STRING[6]

HHD07_[I] (Activity of HH member) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Which of the items best describes what **CollectionMember** is mainly doing at present?

In education or training

Employed

Self-employed

Helping family member in a family farm or business

Unemployed

Retired

In military or civic service

Taking care of the home or family

On maternity or paternity leave

On parental leave or childcare leave

Ill or disabled for a long time or permanently

Other

HHD08_[I] (Relationship satisfaction with HH member) (DontKnow, Refusal)

How satisfied are you with your relationship with **CollectionMember**?

On a scale from 0 to 10 where 0 means 'not at all satisfied' and 10 means 'completely satisfied' and 5 means 'about average', what number best represents your satisfaction with your relationship?

HHD09_[I] (Disability of HH member) (DontKnow, Refusal)

For the past six months at least, to what extent has **CollectionMember** been limited because of a health problem in activities people usually do? Would you say they have been...

Severely limited

Limited, but not severely

Not limited

IF (HHD06_ = RESPONSE)

▪

CHECK: (((len(HHD06_) = 6)AND(val(substring(HHD06_, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(HHD06_, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(HHD06_, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)]

ENDIF

ENDLOOP

ENDIF

IF (corespartner = 1)

○

HHD11 (Household Tasks Intro) (Empty)

The next questions are about who does what in your household. Please indicate who does the following tasks in your household.

HHD11a (Household Tasks: Preparing meals) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Preparing daily meals

Always me

Usually me

Equally me and partner

Usually partner

Always partner

Always or usually someone else

HHD11b (Household Tasks: Vacuuming) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Vacuum cleaning the house

Always me

Usually me

Equally me and partner

Usually partner

Always partner

Always or usually someone else

HHD11c (Household Tasks: Doing laundry) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Doing the laundry

Always me
Usually me
Equally me and partner
Usually partner
Always partner
Always or usually someone else

HHD11d (Household Tasks: Small repairs) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Doing small repairs in and around the house

Always me
Usually me
Equally me and partner
Usually partner
Always partner
Always or usually someone else

HHD11e (Household Tasks: Finances) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Paying bills and keeping financial records

Always me
Usually me
Equally me and partner
Usually partner
Always partner
Always or usually someone else

HHD11f (Household Tasks: Social) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Organising joint social activities

Always me
Usually me
Equally me and partner
Usually partner
Always partner
Always or usually someone else

HHD12 (Household tasks satisfaction) (DontKnow, Refusal)

How satisfied are you with the division of household tasks between you and your partner? On a scale from 0 to 10 where 0 means 'not at all satisfied' and 10 means 'completely satisfied' and 5 means 'about average', what number best represents your satisfaction with the division of household tasks?

NUMBER [0..10]

IF (hasyoungchild = yes)

■

HHD13 (Childcare Tasks Intro) (Empty)

The next statements are about various tasks that have to be done when one lives together with children. Please indicate, who in your household does these tasks?

HHD13a (Childcare Tasks: Dressing) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

Dressing the children or seeing that the children are properly dressed

Always me
Usually me
Equally me and partner
Usually partner
Always partner
Always or usually someone else
Children do it themselves

HHD13b (Childcare Tasks: Stay with ill children) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

Staying at home with the children when they are ill

Always me
Usually me
Equally me and partner
Usually partner
Always partner
Always or usually someone else
Children do it themselves

HHD13c (Childcare Tasks: Playing with children) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

Playing with the children and/or taking part in leisure activities with them

Always me
Usually me
Equally me and partner
Usually partner
Always partner
Always or usually someone else
Children do it themselves

HHD13e (Childcare Tasks: Putting children to bed) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

Putting the children to bed

Always me
Usually me
Equally me and partner
Usually partner
Always partner
Always or usually someone else
Children do it themselves

IF (childover6 = yes)

- HHD13d (Childcare Tasks: Homework) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)
Helping the children with homework
Always me
Usually me
Equally me and partner
Usually partner
Always partner
Always or usually someone else
Children do it themselves

ENDIF

HHD14 (Childcare tasks satisfaction) (DontKnow, Refusal)
How satisfied are you with the way childcare tasks are divided between you and your partner?
On a scale from 0 to 10 where 0 means 'not at all satisfied' and 10 means 'completely satisfied' and 5 means 'about average', what number best represents your satisfaction with the way childcare tasks are divided?
NUMBER [0..10]

ENDIF

HHD15 (Decision Making Intro) (Empty)

The next questions are about decisions. Who makes decisions about the following issues in your household?

HHD15a (Decision Making: Routine purchases) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

Routine purchases for the household

Always me
Usually me
Equally me and partner
Usually partner
Always partner
Always or usually someone else

HHD15b (Decision Making: Expensive purchases) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

Occasional more expensive purchases for the household

Always me
Usually me
Equally me and partner
Usually partner
Always partner
Always or usually someone else

HHD15c (Decision Making: Working) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

The time you spend in paid work

Always me
Usually me
Equally me and partner
Usually partner
Always partner
Always or usually someone else

HHD15d (Decision Making: Partners working time) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

The time your partner spends in paid work

Always me
Usually me
Equally me and partner
Usually partner
Always partner
Always or usually someone else

HHD16 (Organisation of income) (DontKnow, Refusal)

How do you and your partner organise your household income? Which of the items fits best?

I manage all the money and give my partner his/her share
My partner manages all the money and gives me my share
We pool all the money and each takes out what we need
We pool some of the money and keep the rest separate
We each keep our own money separate
Other

HHD17 (Organisation of expenses) (DontKnow, Refusal)

How do you manage your monthly expenses that you have together (e.g. rent, food, etc.)?

I pay everything alone

My partner pays everything alone

We pay both to approximately equal shares

We pay both relative to our personal incomes

Both of us are paying some of them, but there is no fixed rule

ENDIF

IF (hasyoungchild = yes)

○

HHD18 (Received regular childcare help) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Over the last 12 months, have you received regular help with childcare from relatives or friends or other people for whom caring for children is not their primary occupation?

Yes

No

IF (HHD18 = yes)

▪

HHD19_ (Received regular childcare help from ...) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

Which people have provided you with regular help with childcare?

Only include people for whom caring for children is not their primary occupation.

SET OF Partner

Son

Daughter

Step-son

Step-daughter

Mother

Father

Step-mother

Step-Father

Partner's mother or step-mother

Partner's father or step-father

Grandparents (my own or partner's)

Grandchild

Sister

Brother

Daughter's partner

Son's partner

Partner's siblings

Other relative

Friend, acquaintance, neighbour, or colleague

Other person

HHD20 (Received regular childcare help [FREQ]) (Refusal, DontKnow)

How frequently did you receive help with childcare?

NUMBER [0..10000]

IF (NOT((HHD20 = DontKnow)OR(HHD20 = Refusal)))

▪

HHD20u (Received regular childcare help [UNIT]) (DontKnow, Refusal, Empty, NA)

hours per...

Week

Month

Year

ENDIF

HHD21 (Paid for regular childcare help) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Were any of these individuals paid for their help?

Yes

No

ENDIF

HHD22 (Regular institutional childcare help) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Do you get regular help with childcare from a day care centre, a nursery or pre-school, an after school care centre, a self-organised childcare group, a babysitter, or from some other institutional or paid arrangement?

Yes

No

IF (HHD22 = yes)

▪

HHD23_ (Childcare providers) (DontKnow, Refusal, Empty)

Please name all the alternatives that are regularly used.

SET OF Babysitter

Day care centre

Nursery or pre-school
After-school care-centre
Self-organised childcare group
Other institutional arrangement
 HHD24 (Childcare costs) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 How much does your household usually pay for childcare, if anything?
 NUMBER [0..9999999]
 IF (NOT(((HHD24 = 0)OR(HHD24 = DontKnow))OR(HHD24 = Refusal))))

- HHD24u (Childcare costs [UNIT]) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 per...
Week
Month
Year

ENDIF

ENDIF

ENDIF

HHD24a (Received paid housework help) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 Does your household regularly pay someone to do housework?
Yes
No

HHD25 (Childcare help for others) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 Over the last 12 months, have you given help with childcare to other people?
 If the provision of childcare is your job, please consider only the help you have given outside your professional activities.
Yes
No

IF (HHD25 = yes)

- HHD26_ (Given help with childcare to ...) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 To whom have you given this help? Please select all answers that apply.
 SET OF Partner
Son
Daughter
Step-son
Step-daughter
Mother
Father
Step-mother
Step-Father
Partner's mother or step-mother
Partner's father or step-father
Grandparents (my own or partner's)
Grandchild
Sister
Brother
Daughter's partner
Son's partner
Partner's siblings
Other relative
Friend, acquaintance, neighbour, or colleague
Other person

ENDIF

HHD28 (Received regular help with HH tasks) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)
 Over the last 12 months, have you received regular help with household tasks from people for whom these household chores are not their professional job?
 Household tasks include such things as preparing daily meals, vacuum cleaning the house, doing the laundry, doing small repairs in and around the house, paying bills and keeping financial records.
Yes
No

IF (HHD28 = yes)

- HHD29_ (Received regular help with HH tasks from ...) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)
 Which people have provided you with regular help with household tasks?
 Only include people for whom these household chores are not their professional job.
 Household tasks include such things as preparing daily meals, vacuum cleaning the house, doing the laundry, doing small repairs in and around the house, paying bills and keeping financial records.

SET OF Partner
Son
Daughter
Step-son
Step-daughter
Mother
Father
Step-mother
Step-Father
Partner's mother or step-mother
Partner's father or step-father
Grandparents (my own or partner's)
Grandchild
Sister
Brother
Daughter's partner
Son's partner
Partner's siblings
Other relative
Friend, acquaintance, neighbour, or colleague
Other person

ENDIF

HHD35 (Given help with HH tasks) (DontKnow, Refusal)

During the last 12 months, have you given regular help with household tasks to people who do not live in your household? If taking care of household tasks is your job, please consider only the help you have given outside your professional activities.

Household tasks include such things as preparing daily meals, vacuum cleaning the house, doing the laundry, doing small repairs in and around the house, paying bills and keeping financial records.

Yes

No

IF (HHD35 = yes)

HHD36_ (Given help with HH tasks to ...) (DontKnow, Refusal)

To whom have you given this help? Please select all that apply.

Household tasks include such things as preparing daily meals, vacuum cleaning the house, doing the laundry, doing small repairs in and around the house, paying bills and keeping financial records.

SET OF Partner

Son

Daughter

Step-son

Step-daughter

Mother

Father

Step-mother

Step-Father

Partner's mother or step-mother

Partner's father or step-father

Grandparents (my own or partner's)

Grandchild

Sister

Brother

Daughter's partner

Son's partner

Partner's siblings

Other relative

Friend, acquaintance, neighbour, or colleague

Other person

ENDIF

GENINT (Generations Intro) (Empty)

SECTION 5/9: About your background and childhood...

We will now ask you some questions about your parents, background and childhood.

IF (mumcores = no)

GEN01 (Biological mother still alive) (Refusal)

Is your biological mother still alive?

Yes, still alive

No, not alive anymore

I do not know whether she is still alive
I do not know anything

ENDIF
IF (dadcores = no)

- - GEN02 (Biological father still alive) (Refusal)
 - Is your biological father still alive?
 - Yes, still alive*
 - No, not alive anymore*
 - I do not know whether he is still alive*
 - I do not know anything*

ENDIF
IF (((mumcores = no)AND(dadcores = no))AND(GEN02 = yes))AND(GEN01 = yes))

- - GEN03 (Parents live together) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 - Are your biological father and mother still living together?
 - Yes*
 - No*

ENDIF
IF (mumcores = no)

- - GEN09 (Mothers date of birth) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 - When was your biological mother born? [MM/YYYY]
 - If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.
 - MM/YYYY
 - Vertical
 - STRING[6]*
 - IF (GEN09 = RESPONSE)
 - - CHECK: (((len(GEN09) = 6)AND(val(substring(GEN09, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(GEN09, 3, 4)) > 1870))AND(val(substring(GEN09, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)]*

ENDIF
ENDIF
IF (GEN01 = no)

- - GEN10 (Mothers date of death) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 - When did your mother pass away? [MM/YYYY]
 - If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.
 - MM/YYYY
 - Vertical
 - 99/9999
 - STRING[6]*
 - IF (GEN10 = RESPONSE)
 - - CHECK: (((len(GEN10) = 6)AND(val(substring(GEN10, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(GEN10, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(GEN10, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)]*

ENDIF
ENDIF
GEN11 (Mother born in country) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Was your biological mother born in 18;?

Yes

No

IF (GEN11 = no)

- - GEN12 (Mothers country of birth) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 - In which country was she born?
 - Please type in (the first letters of) the country and then select the country from the list by clicking on it.
 - STRING*
 - JOBCODER: Cntfile3**

ENDIF
IF ((GEN01 = yes)AND(mumcores = no))

- - GEN15a (Meetings with mother [FREQ]) (Never, DontKnow, Refusal)
 - How often do you meet with your biological mother in person?
 - NUMBER [0..365]*

```

IF (NOT(((GEN15a = never)OR(GEN15a = DontKnow))OR(GEN15a = Refusal)))
  ■ 
    GEN15au (Meetings with mother [UNIT]) (DontKnow, Refusal)
      times a...
      Week
      Month
      Year
ENDIF
GEN15b (Contact with mother [FREQ]) (Never, DontKnow, Refusal)
  How often do you have contact with your biological mother by phone, mail, email or any
  other electronic means?
  NUMBER [0..365]
IF (NOT(((GEN15b = never)OR(GEN15b = DontKnow))OR(GEN15b = Refusal)))
  ■ 
    GEN15bu (Contact with mother [UNIT]) (DontKnow, Refusal)
      times a...
      Week
      Month
      Year
ENDIF
GEN16 (Relationship satisfaction with mother) (DontKnow, Refusal)
  How satisfied are you with the relationship with your biological mother?
  On a scale from 0 to 10 where 0 means 'not at all satisfied' and 10 means 'completely sat-
  isfied' and 5 means 'about average', what number best represents your satisfaction with
  your relationship with your mother?
  NUMBER [0..10]
ENDIF
IF (dadcores = no)
  ○ 
    GEN23 (Fathers date of birth) (DontKnow, Refusal)
      When was your biological father born? [MM/YYYY]
      If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.
      MM/YYYY
      Vertical
      99/9999
      STRING[6]
    IF (GEN23 = RESPONSE)
      ■ 
        CHECK: (((len(GEN23) = 6)AND(val(substring(GEN23, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(sub-
        string(GEN23, 3, 4)) > 1870))AND(val(substring(GEN23, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [Please enter
        a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)]
    ENDIF
  ENDIF
ENDIF
IF (GEN02 = no)
  ○ 
    GEN24 (Fathers date of death) (DontKnow, Refusal)
      When did your father pass away? [MM/YYYY]
      If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.
      MM/YYYY
      Vertical
      99/9999
      STRING[6]
    IF (GEN24 = RESPONSE)
      ■ 
        CHECK: (((len(GEN24) = 6)AND(val(substring(GEN24, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(sub-
        string(GEN24, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(GEN24, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [Please enter
        a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)]
    ENDIF
  ENDIF
ENDIF
GEN25 (Father born in country) (DontKnow, Refusal)
  Was your biological father born in 18;?
  Yes
  No
IF (GEN25 = no)
  ○ 
    GEN26 (Fathers country of birth) (DontKnow, Refusal)
      In which country was he born?
      Please type in (the first letters of) the country and then select the country from the list by
      clicking on it.

```

```

    STRING
    JOBCODER: Cntfile4
ENDIF
IF ((GEN02 = yes)AND(dadcores = no))
    ◻
    ○ GEN29a (Meetings with father [FREQ]) (Never, DontKnow, Refusal)
      How often do you meet with your biological father in person?
      Vertical
      NUMBER [0..365]
      IF (NOT(((GEN29a = never)OR(GEN29a = DontKnow))OR(GEN29a = Refusal))))
          ■ ◻
          GEN29au (Meetings with father [UNIT]) (DontKnow, Refusal)
            times a...
            Vertical
            Week
            Month
            Year
      ENDIF
    GEN29b (Contact with father [FREQ]) (Never, DontKnow, Refusal)
      How often do you have contact with your biological father by phone, mail, email or any
      other electronic means?
      NUMBER [0..365]
      IF (NOT(((GEN29b = never)OR(GEN29b = DontKnow))OR(GEN29b = Refusal))))
          ■ ◻
          GEN29bu (Contact with father [UNIT]) (DontKnow, Refusal)
            times a...
            Week
            Month
            Year
      ENDIF
    GEN30 (Relationship satisfaction with father) (DontKnow, Refusal)
      How satisfied are you with the relationship with your biological father?
      On a scale from 0 to 10 where 0 means 'not at all satisfied' and 10 means 'completely sat-
      isfied' and 5 means 'about average', what number best represents your satisfaction with
      your relationship with your father?
      NUMBER [0..10]
ENDIF
GEN37a (Biological parents married) (DontKnow, Refusal)
  We are now going to ask you some questions about your family background and childhood. Did
  your biological parents ever get married?
  Yes
  No
IF (GEN37a = yes)
    ◻
    ○ GEN37 (Date of parents marriage) (DontKnow, Refusal)
      When did they get married? [MM/YYYY]
      If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.
      MM/YYYY
      Vertical
      99/9999
      STRING[6]
      IF (GEN37 = RESPONSE)
          ■ ◻
          CHECK: (((len(GEN37) = 6)AND(val(substring(GEN37, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(sub-
          string(GEN37, 3, 4) > 1900))AND(val(substring(GEN37, 3, 4) < 2023))) [Please enter
          a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)]
      ENDIF
    ENDIF
ENDIF
GEN38a (Biological parents broke Up) (DontKnow, Refusal)
  Did your biological parents ever break up?
  Yes
  No
  Not applicable, never together
IF (GEN38a = yes)
    ◻
    ○ GEN38b (Date of parents break up) (DontKnow, Refusal)
      When did that first happen? [MM/YYYY]
      If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.
      MM/YYYY

```

Vertical
99/9999
STRING[6]
IF (GEN38b = RESPONSE)

- CHECK: (((len(GEN38b) = 6)AND(val(substring(GEN38b, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(GEN38b, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(GEN38b, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)]

ENDIF
ENDIF
GEN39a (Brothers [NUMBER]) (DontKnow, Refusal)
How many brothers do you have? Including those who are deceased.
NUMBER [0..20]
GEN39b (Sisters [NUMBER]) (DontKnow, Refusal)
How many sisters do you have? Including those who are deceased.
NUMBER [0..20]
IF (GEN39aGEN39b > 0)

- GEN40 (Birth order of respondent) (DontKnow, Refusal)
How many of your siblings are older than you? Including those who are deceased
If you and your sibling(s) are twins, do not count your twin as an older sibling. Enter 0 if you do not have other older siblings.
NUMBER [0..20]

ENDIF
GEN41a (Mothers first birth [YEAR]) (DontKnow, Refusal)
In which year did your biological mother first give birth?
YYYY
Vertical
NUMBER [1900..2030]
GEN41b (Fathers first birth [YEAR]) (DontKnow, Refusal)
In which year did your biological father have his first child?
YYYY
Vertical
NUMBER [1900..2030]
GEN42 (Residence during childhood) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Where did you live for most of your childhood, that is until you were 15?
In TOSTRING(acountry)
Abroad
IF (GEN42 = incountry)

- GEN43 (Place of childhood residence) (DontKnow, Refusal)
In which region did you live?
Drenthe
Flevoland
Friesland
Gelderland
Groningen
Limburg
North Brabant
North Holland
Overijssel
South Holland
Utrecht
Zeeland

ENDIF
IF (GEN42 = abroad)

- GEN44a (Country of residence in childhood) (DontKnow, Refusal)
In which country did you live?
Please type in (the first letters of) the country and then select the country from the list by clicking on it.
STRING
JOB CODER: Cntfile5

ENDIF
IF (GEN42 = incountry)

- GEN44b (Lived abroad for more than a year) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Did you ever live abroad for more than three months during your childhood, that is until you were 15?

Yes
No

ENDIF

GEN45 (Lived with both parents in childhood) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Did you live most of your childhood up to the age of 15 with both of your own biological parents?

Yes
No

IF (GEN45 = no)

GEN46 (With whom R lived until age 15) (DontKnow, Refusal)

With whom did you live for most of your childhood, that is, until you were 15?

With biological mother only
With biological father only
With biological mother and stepfather
With biological father and stepmother
With (a) grandparent(s)
With (an) other relative(s)
With (an) adoptive parent(s)
With (a) foster parent(s)
In a boarding school
In an orphanage
In a youth home
Other

ENDIF

GENINT2 (Generations Intro2) (Empty)

The next set of questions refer to the parents (including step-parents and foster parents) you lived with most of the time up to age 15.

GEN47 (Parents relationship in Rs childhood) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

How was the relationship between your parents up to the time you were 15 years of age?

Taking all things together, on a scale from 0 to 10, where 0 is really bad and 10 is absolutely perfect, how would you describe the relationship between your parents at that time?

Vertical

NUMBER [0..10]

GEN48 (Fathers occupation in Rs childhood) (Home, DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

What was your father's occupation when you were 15?

Please type in your father's occupation and click on the best description from the list that will appear.

STRING

JOB CODER: OccFile1

GEN49 (Fathers highest education level [ISCED]) (DontKnow, Refusal)

What is the highest level of education that your father has successfully completed?

Early childhood education
Primary education
Lower secondary education
Upper secondary education
Post-secondary non tertiary education
Short cycle tertiary education
Bachelor or equivalent
Master or equivalent
Doctoral or equivalent

GEN50 (Mothers occupation in Rs childhood) (Home, DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

What was your mother's occupation when you were 15?

Please type in your mother's occupation and click on the best description from the list that will appear.

STRING

JOB CODER: OccFile2

GEN51 (Mothers highest education level [ISCED]) (DontKnow, Refusal)

What is the highest level of education that your mother has successfully completed?

Early childhood education
Primary education
Lower secondary education
Upper secondary education
Post-secondary non tertiary education
Short cycle tertiary education
Bachelor or equivalent
Master or equivalent
Doctoral or equivalent

IF ((mumcores = yes) OR (dadcores = yes))

GEN52 (Ever lived separately from parents) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Have you ever lived separately from your parents for at least three months?

```

        Yes
        No
ENDIF
IF ((GEN52 = yes)OR((mumcores = no)AND(dadcores = no)))
    ◻
    ◦ GEN52a (Date moved out from parents) (DontKnow, Refusal)
      When did you for the first time start living separately from your parents for at least three
      months? [MM/YYYY]
      If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.
      MM/YYYY
      Vertical
      99/9999
      STRING[6]
      IF (GEN52a = RESPONSE)
          ◻
          CHECK: (((len(GEN52a) = 6)AND(val(substring(GEN52a, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(sub-
          string(GEN52a, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(GEN52a, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [Please enter
          a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)]
      ENDIF
    ENDIF
ENDIF
IF (((GEN52 = no)OR(mumcores = yes))OR(dadcores = yes))
    ◻
    ◦ GEN53 (Intention to live separate from parents) (Refusal)
      Do you intend to start living separately from your parents within the next 3 years?
      Definitely not
      Probably not
      Unsure
      Probably yes
      Definitely yes
    ENDIF
ENDIF
GEN54 (Grandparents alive [NUMBER]) (DontKnow, Refusal)
  How many of your grandparents are alive?
  NUMBER [0..10]
IF (totalchildren > 0)
    ◻
    ◦ GEN55 (Has grandchild) (DontKnow, Refusal)
      Do you have any grandchildren?
      Yes
      No
    ENDIF
ENDIF
IF (GEN55 = yes)
    ◻
    ◦ GEN56 (Grandchildren [NUMBER]) (DontKnow, Refusal)
      How many grandchildren do you have?
      NUMBER [1..99]
      GEN57 (Grandchilds date of birth) (DontKnow, Refusal)
        When was your oldest grandchild born? [MM/YYYY]
        If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.
        MM/YYYY
        Vertical
        99/9999
        STRING[6]
        IF (GEN57 = RESPONSE)
            ◻
            CHECK: (((len(GEN57) = 6)AND(val(substring(GEN57, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(sub-
            string(GEN57, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(GEN57, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [Please enter
            a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)]
        ENDIF
    ENDIF
ENDIF
GEN58 (Need for regular help with personal care) (DontKnow, Refusal)
  Do you need regular help with personal care such as dressing, bathing or showering, eating, get-
  ting in or out of bed, using the toilet?
  Yes
  No
IF (GEN58 = yes)
    ◻
    ◦ GEN59 ( Received regular personal care) (DontKnow, Refusal)

```

Over the last 12 months, is there any person who has helped you regularly with personal care, such as dressing, bathing or showering, eating, getting in or out of bed, using the toilet?

Yes

No

IF (GEN59 = yes)

■

GEN60_ (Received help personal care from ...) (DontKnow, Refusal)

From whom did you receive this assistance? Please select all answers that apply.

SET OF Partner

Son

Daughter

Step-son

Step-daughter

Mother

Father

Step-mother

Step-Father

Partner's mother or step-mother

Partner's father or step-father

Grandparents (my own or partner's)

Grandchild

Sister

Brother

Daughter's partner

Son's partner

Partner's siblings

Other relative

Friend, acquaintance, neighbour, or colleague

Other person

ENDIF

GEN63 (Received regular professional care) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Over the last 12 months, have you received regular help with personal care from professional persons from the public sector or from a private organisation?

Yes, from a public sector organisation

Yes, from a private sector organisation

Yes, but not sure of organization type

No

ENDIF

GEN66 (Given personal care) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Over the last 12 months, have you given any person inside or outside the household regular help with personal care, such as washing, getting out of bed, or dressing?

Yes

No

IF (GEN66 = yes)

○

GEN67_ (Given personal care to ...) (DontKnow, Refusal)

To whom have you given this help? Please select all answers that apply.

SET OF Partner

Son

Daughter

Step-son

Step-daughter

Mother

Father

Step-mother

Step-Father

Partner's mother or step-mother

Partner's father or step-father

Grandparents (my own or partner's)

Grandchild

Sister

Brother

Daughter's partner

Son's partner

Partner's siblings

Other relative

Friend, acquaintance, neighbour, or colleague

Other person

ENDIF

GEN68 (Received financial transfer) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Please think of the last 12 months. Not counting any shared housing or shared food, have you [or your partner] received any financial or material gift from anyone inside or outside this household amounting to at least €250?

Yes

No

IF (GEN68 = yes)

GEN69_ (Received financial support from ...) (DontKnow, Refusal)

From whom have you received this support? Please select all answers that apply.

SET OF Partner

Son

Daughter

Step-son

Step-daughter

Mother

Father

Step-mother

Step-Father

Partner's mother or step-mother

Partner's father or step-father

Grandparents (my own or partner's)

Grandchild

Sister

Brother

Daughter's partner

Son's partner

Partner's siblings

Other relative

Friend, acquaintance, neighbour, or colleague

Other person

ENDIF

GEN70 (Given financial transfer) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Over the last 12 months, have you [or your partner] given any goods or money to another person inside or outside this household?

Please consider only gifts of a value of at least €250 and do not count shared housing or shared food.

Yes

No

IF (GEN70 = yes)

GEN71_ (Given financial transfer to ...) (DontKnow, Refusal)

To whom have you given this support? Please select all answers that apply.

SET OF Partner

Son

Daughter

Step-son

Step-daughter

Mother

Father

Step-mother

Step-Father

Partner's mother or step-mother

Partner's father or step-father

Grandparents (my own or partner's)

Grandchild

Sister

Brother

Daughter's partner

Son's partner

Partner's siblings

Other relative

Friend, acquaintance, neighbour, or colleague

Other person

ENDIF

WELINT (Wellbeing Intro) (Empty)

SECTION 6/9: About your health and wellbeing...

We would now like to ask you some questions about your general wellbeing and health status.

WEL01 (Life satisfaction) (DontKnow, Refusal)

All things considered, how satisfied are you with your life as a whole nowadays?

Please note that 0 means 'extremely dissatisfied' and 10 means 'extremely satisfied'.

NUMBER [0..10]
 WEL02 (Subjective health) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 How is your health in general?
 Very good
 Good
 Fair
 Bad
 Very bad
 IF (haspartner = yes)

- - WEL02a (Healthcare autonomy) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)
 Who usually makes decisions about health care for yourself?
 Always me
 Usually me
 Equally me and partner
 Usually partner
 Always partner
 Always or usually someone else

ENDIF
 WEL03_ (Health conditions) (Nota, DontKnow, Refusal, Empty)
 Has a doctor ever told you that you had any of the following conditions? Please choose all that apply to you.
 SET OF A heart attack or any other heart problem
 High blood pressure or hypertension
 High blood cholesterol
 A stroke or cerebral vascular disease
 Diabetes or high blood sugar
 Chronic lung disease such as chronic bronchitis or emphysema
 Asthma
 Cancer or malignant tumour, excluding minor skin cancers
 Stomach or duodenal ulcer, peptic ulcer
 Parkinson disease
 Cataracts
 Hip fracture
 Other fractures
 Alzheimer's disease, dementia, or any other serious memory impairment
 Mood or emotional disorders, including anxiety, or any other psychiatric problem
 Rheumatoid arthritis
 Osteoarthritis, or other rheumatism
 Chronic kidney disease
 Other condition, not yet mentioned
 WEL04 (Limitation of daily activities) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 For the past six months at least, to what extent have you been limited because of a health problem in activities people usually do? Would you say they have been...
 Severely limited
 Limited, but not severely
 Not limited
 IF ((WEL04 = severely)OR(WEL04 = notseverly))

- - WEL05 (Duration of limitation) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 How long have you been limited in your ability to carry out normal everyday activities
 Less than 6 months
 6 months to 1 year
 1 year to 5 years
 5 years to 10 years
 10 years or more
 Since childhood

ENDIF
 WEL06 (Weight (kg)) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 Approximately how much do you weigh (in kilograms)?
 NUMBER [25..200]
 WEL07 (Height (cm)) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 Approximately how tall are you (in centimeters)?
 NUMBER [50..300]
 WEL08 (Happiness scale) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 Taking all things together, how happy would you say you are? Please note that 0 means 'extremely unhappy' and 10 means 'extremely happy'
 NUMBER [0..10]
 WEL09 (Loneliness: Intro) (Empty)
 The next six statements are about your current experiences.
 Please indicate for each of them to what extent they have applied to you recently.

WEL09a (Loneliness: People to lean on) (DontKnow, Refusal)
There are plenty of people I can rely on when I have problems
Yes
More or less
No

WEL09b (Loneliness: General sense of emptiness) (DontKnow, Refusal)
I experience a general sense of emptiness
Yes
More or less
No

WEL09c (Loneliness: Miss having people around) (DontKnow, Refusal)
I miss having people around
Yes
More or less
No

WEL09d (Loneliness: Many people I can trust) (DontKnow, Refusal)
There are many people I can trust completely
Yes
More or less
No

WEL09e (Loneliness: Feel rejected) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Often, I feel rejected
Yes
More or less
No

WEL09f (Loneliness: Enough people I feel close) (DontKnow, Refusal)
There are enough people that I feel close to
Yes
More or less
No

WEL10_ (Discuss important matters with ...) (Nobody, DontKnow, Refusal, Empty)
Who are the people with whom you typically discuss important personal matters? You can select multiple answers.
SET OF Partner
Son
Daughter
Step-son
Step-daughter
Mother
Father
Step-mother
Step-Father
Partner's mother or step-mother
Partner's father or step-father
Grandparents (my own or partner's)
Grandchild
Sister
Brother
Daughter's partner
Son's partner
Partner's siblings
Other relative
Friend, acquaintance, neighbour, or colleague
Other person

WEL11 (Depression: Intro) (Empty)
Please indicate how frequently did you experience the following during the previous week.

WEL11a (Depression: Couldn't shake off the blues) (DontKnow, Refusal)
I felt that I could not shake off the blues even with help from my family or friends
Never
Sometimes
Often
Most or all of the time

WEL11b (Depression: Felt depressed) (DontKnow, Refusal)
I felt depressed
Never
Sometimes
Often
Most or all of the time

WEL11c (Depression: Felt life was a failure) (DontKnow, Refusal)
I thought my life had been a failure
Never
Sometimes

Often
Most or all of the time
WEL11d (Depression: Felt fearful) (DontKnow, Refusal)
I felt fearful

Never
Sometimes
Often
Most or all of the time

WEL11e (Depression: Felt sad) (DontKnow, Refusal)
I felt sad
Never
Sometimes
Often
Most or all of the time

WRKINT (Work Intro) (Empty)

SECTION 7/9: About your work...

Now we would like to ask some questions about your (and your partner's) employment status
IF (NOT(((BDEMOGRAPHICS.DEM06 = other)OR(BDEMOGRAPHICS.DEM06 = DontKnow))OR(BDEMOGRAPHICS.DEM06 = Refusal)))

○

WRK01 (Satisfaction with Employment Status) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Early in the interview you mentioned that you are ComposedName. How satisfied are you with being ComposedName?

On a scale from 0 to 10 where 0 means 'not at all satisfied' and 10 means 'completely satisfied' and 5 means 'about average'?

NUMBER [0..10]

WRK03 (Date of starting status) (DontKnow, Refusal)

When did this period of 'ComposedName' begin? [MM/YYYY]

If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

MM/YYYY

Vertical
99/9999

STRING[6]

IF (WRK03 = RESPONSE)

▪

CHECK: (((len(WRK03) = 6)AND(val(substring(WRK03, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(WRK03, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(WRK03, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)]

ENDIF

ENDIF

WRK02 (Employment status) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Have you been in paid work in the last week?

In paid work refers to someone who either:

a) worked for pay, profit or family gain for at least one hour in the last week or;

b) were not at work during the last week but has a job or business from which they were temporarily absent (i.e. on holiday or some form of leave)

In paid work

Not in paid work, but looking for work

Not in paid work and not looking for work

IF (WRK02 = 1)

○

WRK04 (Occupation) (DontKnow, Refusal)

What is your current occupation? Please type in your current occupation and click on the best description from the list that will appear.

If you are engaged in two or more jobs or businesses, please consider only the one in which you spend most of your working hours.

STRING

JOBCODER: OccFile3

WRK06 (Work time) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Is your work full time or part time?

Full time

Part time

WRK07 (Hours worked per week) (DontKnow, Refusal)

How many hours per week do you normally work in this job or business including overtime?

NUMBER [0..200]

WRK08 (Commute time [MIN]) (WrkHome, DontKnow, Refusal)

On a normal workday, how long does it take to get from home to your main place of work? Please provide an answer in hours and minutes [HH:MM]

```

--:--
Vertical
STRING[5]
WRK09 (Fixed start and finish times) (DontKnow, Refusal)
  Within your regular or normal pattern of work, is it usual for you to work with fixed start-
  ing and finishing times?
  Yes
  No
WRK10 (Work from home) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)
  Thinking about the last four weeks, did you do any work at home, including using internet
  for professional purpose, checking emails, having professional phone calls?
  Yes, twice or more per week
  Yes, less than twice per week
  No
WRK11 (Evening work) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)
  Thinking about the last four weeks, did you ever work for at least 2 hours in the evening
  or at night (between 8 p.m. and 5 a.m.)?
  Yes, twice or more per week
  Yes, less than twice per week
  No
IF ((WRK11 = yes2plus)OR(WRK11 = yes2minus))
  ■ 
    WRK12 (Evening work location) (DontKnow, Refusal)
      Was this work mainly done at home or somewhere else?
      At home
      Somewhere else
      it varies
ENDIF
WRK13 (Weekend work) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)
  Thinking of the last four weeks, did you work on Saturdays or Sundays?
  Yes, twice or more in the last four weeks
  Yes, less than twice in the last four weeks
  No
IF ((WRK13 = yes2plus)OR(WRK13 = yes2minus))
  ■ 
    WRK14 (Weekend work location) (DontKnow, Refusal)
      Was this work mainly done at home or somewhere else?
      At home
      Somewhere else
      it varies
ENDIF
WRK15 (Work Balance: Intro) (Empty)
  How often has each of the following happened to you during the past three months?
WRK15a (Work Balance: Too tired to do chores) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)
  I have come home from work too tired to do the chores that need to be done
  Several times a week
  Several times a month
  Once or twice a month
  Never
WRK15b (Work Balance: Hard fulfil family duties) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)
  It has been difficult for me to fulfil my family responsibilities because of the amount of
  time I spent on my job
  Several times a week
  Several times a month
  Once or twice a month
  Never
WRK15c (Work Balance: Too tired function at work) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)
  I have arrived at work too tired to function well because of the household work I had done
  Several times a week
  Several times a month
  Once or twice a month
  Never
WRK15d (Work Balance: Hard to concentrate at work) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)
  I have found it difficult to concentrate at work because of my family responsibilities
  Several times a week
  Several times a month
  Once or twice a month
  Never
WRK16a (Likelihood of job loss in 12m) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)
  How likely is it that you will lose your job in the next twelve months?

```

Very unlikely
Unlikely
Unsure
Likely
Very likely

WRK16b (Intention to give up work) (Refusal)

Do you intend to give up paid work in the next three years?

Definitely not
Probably not
Unsure
Probably yes
Definitely yes

IF (NOT(BDEMOGRAPHICS.DEM06 = 3))

▪

WRK17 (Organization type) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Is the business or organisation where you work private, public or mixed?

Private
Public
Mixed

WRK18 (Current contract type) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Is your current work contract, if you have any, a permanent contract, a fixed term contract, or a temporary contract?

Permanent
Fixed term
Temporary
No written contract

WRK20 (Flexible work arrangements) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Does your employer allow regular flexible time arrangements for personal reasons, like for adapting to children's schedules?

Yes
No

WRK21 (Additional job or business) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Do you currently earn money from an additional job or business?

Yes
No

IF (WRK21 = yes)

▪

WRK22 (Work hours in additional job or business) (DontKnow, Refusal)

How many hours per week do you normally work in your additional job or business including overtime?

NUMBER [0..200]

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF (BDEMOGRAPHICS.DEM06 = 3)

▪

WRK23 (Employees [NUMBER]) (DontKnow, Refusal)

How many paid employees do you have, including family members who work for pay?

NUMBER [0..1000000]

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF ((BDEMOGRAPHICS.DEM06 = 9)OR(BDEMOGRAPHICS.DEM06 = 10))

○

WRK24 (Opportunity to resume work after leave) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

Do you have the opportunity to resume your work after your maternity/parental/childcare leave has ended?

Yes
No

WRK25 (Intention to work after leave) (Refusal)

Do you intend to work after your leave has ended?

Definitely not
Probably not
Unsure
Probably yes
Definitely yes

ENDIF

IF ((WRK02 = 2)OR(WRK02 = 3))

○

WRK26 (Job before current activity) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Did you have a job or business directly before your current status?

Yes

No

IF (WRK26 = yes)

▪

WRK27 (Last occupation) (DontKnow, Refusal)

What was your last occupation? Please describe your last occupation and click on the best description from the list that will appear.

If you were engaged in two or more jobs or businesses, please consider only the one in which you spent most of your working hours.

STRING

JOB CODER: OccFile4

WRK28 (Previous employment status) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Were you...

Employed

Self-employed

In vocational training

Helping family member in a family business or a farm

WRK30 (Reason for stopping work) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Why did you stop working in your previous job or business? Please indicate the main reason.

Laid off (business closure, redundancy, early retirement, dismissal etc.)

Mandatory retirement

End of contract/temporary job

Sale/closure of own or family business

Marriage

Child birth/need to look after children

Need to look after old, sick, disabled person(s)

Partner job required move to another place

Studying

Military or civic service

Own illness or disability

Wanted to retire or to live off private means

Other reason

WRK30a (Date of stopping work) (DontKnow, Refusal)

When did you stop working in your previous job or business? [MM/YYYY]

MM/YYYY

Vertical

99/9999

STRING[6]

IF (WRK30a = RESPONSE)

▪

CHECK: (((len(WRK30a) = 6)AND(val(substring(WRK30a, 1, 2)) <= 12))AND(val(substring(WRK30a, 3, 4)) > 1900))AND(val(substring(WRK30a, 3, 4)) < 2023)) [Please enter a month (e.g. 05) and a year (e.g. 1990)]

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF (WRK02 = 3)

▪

WRK31 (Intention to take job or start business) (Refusal)

Do you intend to take a job or start a business within the next three years?

Definitely not

Probably not

Unsure

Probably yes

Definitely yes

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF (BDEMOGRAPHICS.DEM21 = yes)

○

WRK32 (Activity status) (DontKnow, Refusal)

The next questions are about your partner's present work and daily activities. Early in the interview you mentioned that he/she is ComposedName. We would now like to ask you some more detailed questions about what he/she does. Has your partner been in paid work during the last week?

In paid work refers to someone who either:

a) worked for pay, profit or family gain for at least one hour in the last week or;

b) were not at work during the last week but has a job or business from which they were temporarily absent (i.e. on holiday or some form of leave)

In paid work
Not in paid work, but looking for work
Not in paid work and not looking for work

IF (WRK32 = 1)

- WRK34 (Partners occupation) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)
What is your partner's current occupation? Please type in your partner's current occupation and click on the best description from the list that will appear.
If he/she was engaged in two or more jobs or businesses, please consider only the one in which he/she spent most of their working hours.

STRING

JOBCODER: OccFile5

- WRK35 (Partners work hours) (DontKnow, Refusal)
How many hours per week does your partner normally work in this job or business including overtime?

NUMBER [0..200]

- WRK36 (Partners fixed start and finish times) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Within your partner's regular or normal pattern of work, is it usual for your partner to work with fixed starting and finishing times?

Yes

No

- WRK37 (Partner works from home) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)
Thinking about the last four weeks, did your partner ever do any work at home, including using internet for professional purpose, checking emails, having professional phone calls?

Yes, twice or more per week

Yes, less than twice per week

No

- WRK38 (Partner works in the evening) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)
Thinking about the last four weeks, did your partner work for at least 2 hours in the evening or at night (between 8 p.m. and 5 a.m.)?

Yes, twice or more per week

Yes, less than twice per week

No

IF ((WRK38 = yes2plus)OR(WRK38 = yes2minus))

- WRK39 (Partners evening work location) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Was this work mainly done at home or somewhere else?

At home

Somewhere else

it varies

ENDIF

- WRK40 (Partner works weekends) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)
Thinking of the last four weeks, did your partner work on Saturdays or Sundays?

Yes, twice or more in the last four weeks

Yes, less than twice in the last four weeks

No

IF ((WRK40 = yes2plus)OR(WRK40 = yes2minus))

- WRK41 (Partners weekend work location) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Was this work mainly at home or somewhere else?

At home

Somewhere else

it varies

ENDIF

- WRK42 (Partners likelihood of job loss in 12m) (DontKnow, Refusal)
How likely is it that your partner will lose their job in the next twelve months?

Very unlikely

Unlikely

Unsure

Likely

Very likely

IF (NOT(BDEMOGRAPHICS.DEM26 = 3))

- WRK43 (Partners organization type) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Is the business or organisation where your partner works private, public or mixed?

Private

Public

Mixed

WRK44 (Partners current contract type) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Is your partner's current work contract, if any, a permanent contract, a fixed term contract, or a temporary contract?

Permanent
Fixed term
Temporary
No written contract

WRK46 (Partner has flexible work arrangements) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Does your partner's employer allow regular flexible time arrangements for personal reasons, like for adapting to children schedules?

Yes
No

WRK47 (Partners additional job or business) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Does your partner currently earn money from an additional job or business?

Yes
No

IF (WRK47 = yes)

- WRK48 (Partners work hours in additional job) (DontKnow, Refusal)
How many hours per week does your partner normally work in an additional job or business including overtime?
NUMBER [0..200]

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF (BDEMOGRAPHICS.DEM26 = 3)

- WRK49 (Partners employees [NUMBER]) (DontKnow, Refusal)
How many paid employees does your partner have, including family members who work for pay?
NUMBER [0..1000000]

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF (NOT(WRK32 = 1))

- WRK50 (Partners reason for stopping work) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)
Why did your partner stop working in his or her previous job or business? Please indicate the main reason.
Laid off (business closure, redundancy, early retirement, dismissal etc.)
Mandatory retirement
End of contract/temporary job
Sale/closure of own or family business
Marriage
Child birth/need to look after children
Need to look after old, sick, disabled person(s)
My job required move to another place
Studying
Military or civic service
His/her illness or disability
Wanted to retire or to live off private means
Other Reason

ENDIF

ENDIF

INCINT (Income Intro) (Empty)

SECTION 8/9: About your financial situation...

The next questions are about the financial situation of your household - about the things your household possesses and can afford as well as the income and transfers your household receives.

INC01 (Value of property) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

Taking into account your own accommodation, any secondary homes, ownership of other real estate, including ownership of land - how much would you say they would sell for at today market price?

4,999 € or less
5,000 to 9,999 €
10,000 to 19,999 €
20,000 to 49,999 €
50,000 to 99,999 €
100,000 to 249,999 €
250,000 to 499,999 €
500,000 € or more

INC03 (Can make ends meet) (DontKnow, Refusal)

A household may have different sources of income and more than one household member may contribute to it. Thinking of your household's total monthly income, is your household able to make ends meet...

With great difficulty

With difficulty

With some difficulty

Fairly easily

Easily

Very easily

INC13 (Ever received large financial transfer) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Have you [or your partner] ever received a contribution or inherited money, goods, or property worth more than € 5,000?

Yes

No

IF (INC13 = yes)

INC14_ (Received financial transfer from ...) (DontKnow, Refusal)

From whom did you [or your partner] receive these gifts or inheritances? Please select all answers that apply.

SET OF Partner

Son

Daughter

Step-son

Step-daughter

Mother

Father

Step-mother

Step-Father

Partner's mother or step-mother

Partner's father or step-father

Grandparents (my own or partner's)

Grandchild

Sister

Brother

Daughter's partner

Son's partner

Partner's siblings

Other relative

Friend, acquaintance, neighbour, or colleague

Other person

INC15 (Received large financial transfer [YEAR]) (DontKnow, Refusal)

In which year did you last [or your partner] receive such a large gift or inheritance?

NUMBER [1900..2030]

ENDIF

INC04 (HH can afford: Intro) (Empty)

The next questions are about whether your household can afford to purchase various items, even if they do not want them...

INC04a (HH can afford: Keep house warm) (DontKnow, Refusal)

...keeping your home adequately warm

Yes

No

INC04b (HH can afford: Weeks holiday) (DontKnow, Refusal)

...paying for a week annual holiday away from home

Yes

No

INC04c (HH can afford: Replacing furniture) (DontKnow, Refusal)

...replacing any worn out furniture

Yes

No

INC04d (HH can afford: New clothes) (DontKnow, Refusal)

...replace worn-out clothes with some new ones

Yes

No

INC04e (HH can afford: Eating meat) (DontKnow, Refusal)

...afford a meal with meat, chicken or fish or vegetarian equivalent every second day

Yes

No

INC04f (HH can afford: Entertain friends, family) (DontKnow, Refusal)

...having friends or family for a drink or meal at least once a month

Yes

No

INC04g (HH can afford: Unexpected expenses) (DontKnow, Refusal)

...face unexpected expenses

Yes

No

INC04h (HH can afford: Access to a car) (DontKnow, Refusal)

...have access to a car/van for personal use

Yes

No

INC04i (HH can afford: Two pairs of shoes) (DontKnow, Refusal)

...have two pairs of properly fitting shoes

Yes

No

INC04j (HH can afford: Pocket money) (DontKnow, Refusal)

...spend a small amount of money each week on yourself

Yes

No

INC04k (HH can afford: Leisure activities) (DontKnow, Refusal)

...have regular leisure activities

Yes

No

INC05 (Household has been in arrears) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Has your household been in arrears at any time during the past 12 months, that is unable to pay as scheduled your mortgage, rent, utility bills and/or hire purchase instalments?

Yes

No

INC08_ (Income type) (Nota, DontKnow, Refusal, Empty)

This list shows different types of income. Please indicate which of these types of income your household has received during the last 12 months

SET OF Earnings from your paid work

Earnings from your partner's paid work

A retirement pension

A widow or survivor or war benefit

A disability allowance, incapacity or illness benefit

An unemployment benefit or job seeker allowance

A social assistance payment

A study benefits or a scholarship

A maternity leave, parental leave or childcare leave benefit

Interest, dividends and profits from other investments

Payments from other sources

LOOP I := 1 TO 11

◻

○ IF ((INC08_ > 0) AND (INC08_ < 12))

▪ ◻

INC09_[I] (Income type [FREQ]) (DontKnow, Refusal, Empty)

How many times has your household received 'CollectionMember' during the last 12 months?

INC11_[I] (Income type [RANGE]) (DontKnow, Refusal, Empty)

Please indicate the range of the average amount your household received each time from that payment type.

Please consider the net amount after tax.

499 € or less

500 to 999 €

1,000 to 1,499 €

1,500 to 1,999 €

2,000 to 2,499 €

2,500 to 2,999 €

3,000 to 4,999 €

5,000 € or more

ENDIF

ENDLOOP

INC06 (Total Household Net Income) (DontKnow, Refusal)

If you add up the income from all sources received during the last 12 months, what is your household total net income from all members including yourself?

Please state the net income, which means after deductions for taxes and social security.

4,999 € or less

5,000 to 9,999 €

10,000 to 19,999 €

20,000 to 39,999 €

40,000 to 59,999 €

60,000 to 79,999 €

80,000 to 99,999 €

100,000 € or more

INC12 (Income in 3 years) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Do you think that your financial situation will get better or worse or will be about the same in three years from now?

Much better

Better

Neither better nor worse

Worse

Much worse

ATTINT (Attitudes Intro) (Empty)

SECTION 9/9: About your opinions and views...

The next part of the survey is about your opinions and views. This is very important as we want to understand your perspective on families and relationships.

ATT01 (General trust) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Generally speaking, would you say that most people can be trusted or that you need to be very careful in dealing with people?

Most people can be trusted

Need to be very careful

ATT02 (Future planning) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Do you generally plan for your future or do you just take each day as it comes? Please express your opinion on a scale of 0 to 10 where 0 means 'I plan for my future as much as possible' and 10 means 'I just take each day as it comes'.

NUMBER [0..10]

ATT03 (Values: Intro) (Empty)

To what extent do you agree or disagree with each of the following statements?

ATT03a (Values: Marriage outdated) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Marriage is an out dated institution

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

ATT03b (Values: Unmarried cohabitation) (DontKnow, Refusal)

It is alright for a couple to live together without getting married

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

ATT03d (Values: Divorce is permissible) (DontKnow, Refusal)

It is all right for a couple with an unhappy marriage to get a divorce even if they have children

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

ATT03e (Values: Women need children) (DontKnow, Refusal)

A woman has to have children in order to be fulfilled

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

ATT03g (Values: Child needs a father and mother) (DontKnow, Refusal)

A child needs a home with both a father and a mother to grow up happily

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

ATT03h (Values: Men need children) (DontKnow, Refusal)

A man has to have children in order to be fulfilled

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

ATT03i (Values: Homosexual couple rights) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Homosexual couples should have the same rights as heterosexual couples do

Strongly disagree
Disagree
Neither agree nor disagree
Agree
Strongly agree

ATT03j (Values: Child suffers if mother works) (DontKnow, Refusal)
A pre-school child is likely to suffer if his/her mother works
Strongly disagree
Disagree
Neither agree nor disagree
Agree
Strongly agree

ATT05 (Intergenerational Values: Intro) (Empty)
The next statements are about whether parents should help their adult children

ATT05b (Parents should provide financial help) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Parents ought to provide financial help for their adult children when the children are having financial difficulties
Strongly disagree
Disagree
Neither agree nor disagree
Agree
Strongly agree

ATT06a (Children should care for parents) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Children should take responsibility for caring for their parents when parents are in need
Strongly disagree
Disagree
Neither agree nor disagree
Agree
Strongly agree

ATT06b (Children should financially help parents) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Children ought to provide financial help for their parents when their parents are having financial difficulties
Strongly disagree
Disagree
Neither agree nor disagree
Agree
Strongly agree

ATT07 (Gender Importance: Intro) (Empty)
The next questions are about the roles of men and women

ATT07a (Gender Importance: Political leaders) (DontKnow, Refusal)
On the whole, who would make better political leaders, men or women?
Men definitely
Men slightly
Both sexes Equally
Women slightly
Women definitely

ATT07b (Gender Importance: University) (DontKnow, Refusal)
For whom is a university education more important, men or women?
Men definitely
Men slightly
Both sexes Equally
Women slightly
Women definitely

ATT07c (Gender Importance: Job) (DontKnow, Refusal)
For whom is having a job more important, men or women?
Men definitely
Men slightly
Both sexes Equally
Women slightly
Women definitely

ATT07d (Gender Importance: Childcare) (DontKnow, Refusal)
For whom is looking after the home and children more important, men or women?
Men definitely
Men slightly
Both sexes Equally
Women slightly
Women definitely

ATT07g (Gender Importance: Small children) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Who are better at caring for small children, men or women?
Men definitely
Men slightly
Both sexes Equally

Women slightly
 Women definitely
 ATT11b (Ideal work hours for mothers) (Notall, DontKnow, Refusal)
 Consider a family with a mother, father and a two-year old child. How many hours a week should the mother work?
 Vertical
 NUMBER [0..40]

ATT11d (Ideal work hours for fathers) (Notall, DontKnow, Refusal)
 Consider a family with a mother, father and a two-year old child. How many hours a week should the father work?
 Vertical
 NUMBER [0..40]

ATT08 (Religious denomination) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 Which religious denomination do you adhere to, if any?
 Protestant
 Roman Catholic
 Buddhist
 Hindu
 Muslim
 Jewish
 Sikh
 Orthodox (e.g. Greek or Russian)
 Other Christian
 Other religion
 None

ATT09 (Religious service [FREQ]) (Never, DontKnow, Refusal, NA)
 How often, if at all, do you attend religious services (apart from weddings, funerals, baptisms, and the like)?
 Vertical
 NUMBER [0..365]

IF (NOT((((ATT09 = never)OR(ATT09 = DontKnow))OR(ATT09 = Refusal))OR(ATT09 = NA)))

- - ATT09u (Religious service [UNIT]) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 - times a...
 - Vertical
 - Week
 - Month
 - Year

ENDIF

ATT10 (Religiosity) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 Regardless of whether you belong to a particular religion, how religious would you say you are? Please express your religiosity on a scale of 0 to 10 where 0 means 'Not at all religious' and 10 means 'Very religious'.
 NUMBER [0..10]

IF (mode = f2f)

- - IF (INTERVIEWER)
 - - REP01 (Others present at interview) (DontKnow)
 Were there any other people present during any part of this interview?
 Yes
 No
 - REP02 (Respondent influenced) (DontKnow)
 Did any of these people seem to influence any of the answers given by the respondent?
 A great deal
 A fair amount
 A little
 Not at all
 - IF (((REP02 = greatdeal)OR(REP02 = some))OR(REP02 = little))
 - - REP03 (In what way was R influenced) (DontKnow)
 In what way was the respondent influenced?
 SET OF The person answered the question instead of R
 R was reluctant to answer
 Children were asking for the attention of R
 Other
 - REP04 (Questions where influenced) (DontKnow)
 Questions where influenced
 STRING

ENDIF

REP05 (Willingness to answer questions) (Empty)

All in all, how willing was the respondent to answer the questions?

NUMBER [0..10]

REP06 (Information quality)

How would you judge the information the respondent gave?

NUMBER [0..10]

ENDIF

ENDIF

thanks

Many thanks for your participation in the survey, we greatly appreciate your time. If you have any questions about the survey or would like further information, you can contact us on [TELEPHONE NUMBER] or by emailing [EMAIL ADDRESS].

End interview